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विभेदक अभिव्यक्ति विश्लेषण के आधार पर आम के गुच्छा रोग से
सम्बंधित जीन की पहचान

ASHOK YADAV

**DIVISION OF FRUITS AND HORTICULTURAL TECHNOLOGY
ICAR-INDIAN AGRICULTURAL RESEARCH INSTITUTE
NEW DELHI -110012**

2017

Identification of genes associated with mango malformation through Differential Expression Analysis

A Thesis

By

ASHOK YADAV

**Submitted to the Faculty of Post-Graduate School,
Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi,
in partial fulfillment of the requirements
for the award of the degree of**

DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY

IN

**FRUIT SCIENCE
2017**

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled “**Identification of genes associated with mango malformation through Differential Expression Analysis**” submitted to the Faculty of the Post-Graduate School, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the degree of **Doctor of Philosophy in Fruit Science** is a record of bona fide research work carried out by **Mr. Ashok Yadav, Roll No. 10471** under my guidance and supervision and that no part of this thesis has been submitted for any other degree or diploma.

All the assistance and help or information received during the work on this thesis has been duly acknowledged.

Place: New Delhi

Date: 30.06.2017

(K. Usha)
Chairman,
Advisory Committee

Acknowledgement

Research is an evolving concept. Every result arrived at is a modest beginning for a higher goal. My work in the same spirit is just a step in the ladder. Every effort is motivated by ambition and all ambitious have an inspiration behind. I owe this Putting all things aside, I would like to praise and thank God "**HANUMAN**", the Almighty, the merciful compassionate, who bestowed me with all the favourable circumstances to go through this crucial juncture.

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Needless to say Errors and Omissions are mine.

Place: **I.A.R.I, New Delhi.**

Date: **30th June, 2017.**

(**Ashok Yadav**)

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ABBREVIATIONS

AAO	:	Abscisic-aldehyde oxidase
ABF	:	Abscisic acid responsive elements-binding
AGL	:	Agamous-Like
AHD	:	Arabidopsis Hormone Database
AHK	:	Arabidopsis histidine kinase 3
AHP	:	Arabidopsis histidine-containing phosphotransfer.
AMP-PK	:	AMP-activated protein kinase
AOC	:	Allene oxide cyclase
AOS	:	Allene oxide synthase
AP2	:	Apeta2
ARF	:	Auxin Response Factor 1
ARR-A	:	<i>Arabidopsis</i> Response Regulator A
ARR-B	:	<i>Arabidopsis</i> Response Regulator B
ATH1	:	<i>Arabidopsis Thaliana</i> Homeobox Gene 1
AUX-1	:	Auxin Resistant -1, auxin transporter protein 1
AUX-IAA	:	Auxin indole-3-acetic acid
bHLH	:	Basic Helix-Loop-Helix
BLAST	:	Basic Local Alignment Search Tool
BP	:	Biological Process
BRI1	:	Brassinosteroid insensitive
C4H	:	Cinnamate-4-hydroxylase
CALM	:	Calmodulin
CBL-IPK 2	:	CBL-interacting protein kinase 2-like
CC	:	Cellular Component
CCT	:	CO, CO-like, and Timing of Cab.
CDF1	:	Cycling DOF Factor 1
CDKC2	:	Cyclin-Dependent Kinase
cDNA	:	Complementary DNA
CDPK	:	Cyclin-dependent protein kinase

CDS	:	Coding Sequences
CEBiP	:	Chitin Elicitor-Binding Protein
CKx	:	Cytokinin dehydrogenase
CLF	:	Curly Leaf
CM	:	Chorismate mutase
CML	:	Calcium binding protein calmodulin like
CNGF	:	Cyclic Nucleotide Gated Channel
COG	:	Clusters of Orthologous Groups
COP1	:	Constitutive Photomorphogenic 1
CPD	:	Carboxypeptidase-D
CPK	:	Calcium Dependent Protein Kinase
CPK6	:	Calcium Dependent Protein Kinase 6
CPS	:	Ent-copalyl diphosphate synthase
CRE's	:	Cis regulatory elements
CRY2	:	Cryptochrome 2
CS	:	Chorismate synthase
CTR	:	Constitutive triple response1
CUL3	:	Cullin 3A
CYP-85A1	:	Cytochrome-85A1 family
CYP-85A2	:	Cytochrome-85A2 family
DCL3	:	Dicer-Like 3
DEGs	:	Differentially expressed genes
DET-1	:	De-etiolated 1 homolog
DET-2	:	De-Etiolated 2 Homolog
DWF-1	:	Dwarf-1
DWF-4	:	Dwarf-4
EBF-1/2	:	EIN3 binding F-box protein
EFS	:	Early Flowering In Short Days
EIN-2	:	Ethylene insensitive2
EIN-3	:	Ethylene insensitive3
ELF3	:	Early Flowering 3

EMF2	:	Embryonic Flower 2
ENA	:	European Nucleotide Archive
ERF	:	Ethylene-Responsive Transcription Factor
ERF-1	:	Ethylene Response Factor1
ERF-3	:	Ethylene Response Factor3
ETI	:	Effector-Triggered Immunity
ETR	:	Ethylene receptor1
FC	:	Fold change
FKF1	:	Flavin-Binding Kelch Repeat F box Protein
FLK	:	Flowering Locus KH Domain
FTIP1	:	FT-Interacting Protein 1
GA_{200x3}	:	Gibberellin 20-Oxidase 3
GA_{2-ox}	:	GA ₂ -oxidase
GA_{3-ox}	:	GA ₂ -oxidase
GCT	:	Grand Central
GH3	:	<i>Gretchen Hagen3</i>
GI	:	Gigantea
GID1A	:	Gibberellin Insensitive Dwarf1 A
GID1B	:	GA Insensitive Dwarf 1B
GID1C	:	GA Insensitive Dwarf 1C
GO	:	Gene Ontology
GRAVY	:	Grand Average of Hydropathy
GSH	:	Glutathione
GSL	:	Glucosinolates
GsSRK	:	G-type lectin S-receptor-like ser/threonine-protein kinase
HB-1	:	Healthy bud stage 1
HB16	:	Homeobox Protein 16
HB-2	:	Healthy bud stage 2
HSP	:	Heat Shock Protein
HSTF B2A	:	Heat shock transcription factor B2A
HUB1	:	Histone Mono-Ubiquitination 1

ICS	:	Isochorismate chloroplastic synthase
INO80	:	Inositol Requiring 80
IPT	:	Isopentenyl transferase
JAZ	:	Jasmonate ZIM domain-containing protein
JMJ14	:	Jumonji 14
KAAS	:	KEGG automatic annotation server
KAO	:	Ent-kaurenoic acid oxidase
KEGG	:	Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes
KIN10	:	Kinase 10
KO	:	KEGG Orthology
KO	:	Ent-kaurene oxidase
KS	:	Ent-kaurene synthase
LDL2	:	Lysine Specific Demethylase Like 1
LRB1	:	Light-Response BTB 1
LRR-RLK	:	LRR receptor-like serine/threonine-protein kinase
LWD2	:	Light-Regulated WD 2
MAPK	:	Mitogen-Activated Protein Kinase
MAPKKK	:	Mitogen-Activated Protein Kinase Kinase
MAST	:	Motif Alignment and Search Tool
MB-1	:	Single swollen malformed bud stage I
MB-2	:	Multiple malformed bud stage 2
MB-3	:	Multiple malformed bud stage 3
MBD9	:	Methyl-CPG-Binding Domain 9
MBTFS-1	:	Membrane-Bound Transcription Factor site-1
MF	:	Molecular Function
MPK6	:	Mitogen-activated protein kinase6
MYB30	:	MYB Domain Protein 30
NAC-TF	:	NAM, ATAF & CUC transcription factors
NCBI	:	National Centre for Biotechnology Information
NCED	:	9-cis-epoxycarotenoid dioxygenase
NF-YB1	:	Nuclear Factor Y, Subunit B1

NJ	:	Neighbour Joining
NR database	:	Non Redundant database
NUC	:	Nut-Cracker
PAL	:	Phenylalanine ammonia lyase
PAMPs	:	Pathogen Associated Molecular Pattern
PE Reads	:	Pair End Reads
PIL6	:	Phytochrome-Interacting Factor
PP2C	:	Protein phosphatase 2C
PPI	:	Protein-Protein Interaction
PRR3	:	Pseudo-Response Regulator 3
PTI	:	PAMP triggered immunity
PYR/PYL	:	Pyrabactin Resistance
RAP2.7	:	Related to AP2.7
REF6	:	Relative to Early Flowering
RFI2	:	Red and Far-Red Insensitive 2
RLK	:	Receptor-like protein kinase
RVE2	:	Reveille 2
SAUR	:	Small Auxin Upregulated RNA
SDG25	:	Set Domain Protein 25
Ser/thre PK	:	Serine/threonine-protein kinase
SIMK	:	Salt-Stress-Inducible MAPK
SIMKK	:	SIMK Kinase
SMs	:	Secondary metabolites
SnRK2	:	Serine/threonine-protein kinase SnRK2
SPK	:	Shaggy-related protein kinase
SPL5	:	Squamosa Promoter Binding Protein-LIKE 5
SPL9	:	Squamosa Promoter Binding Protein-Like 9
SSR	:	Simple Sequence Repeats
STRING	:	Search Tool for the Retrieval of Interacting Genes/Proteins
SUS2	:	Sucrose Synthase 2
SUS4	:	Sucrose Synthase 4

SUVR5	:	SU(VAR)3-9-Related Protein 5
SVP	:	Short Vegetative Phase
TAA-1	:	Tryptophan Aminotransferase of <i>Arabidopsis</i> 1
TAIR	:	The Arabidopsis Information Resource
TEM1	:	Tempranillo 1
TF	:	Transcription Factor
TIC	:	Time for Coffee
TIL1	:	Tilted 1
TIR-1	:	Transport Inhibitor Response 1
TMHMM	:	Trans-membrane Helices Hidden Markov Model
TOR	:	Target of rapamycin
TPL	:	Topless
TPS1	:	Trehalose-6-Phosphate Synthase 1
TTF GT-3B	:	Trihelix Transcription Factor GT-3b-like
UBC1	:	Ubiquitin Carrier Protein 1
UBP12	:	Ubiquitin-Specific Protease 12
UGT	:	UDP-glucosyl transferase
VEL1	:	Vernalization 5 -Like 1
VOZ1	:	Vascular Plant one Zinc Finger Protein 1
ZEP	:	Zeaxanthin Epoxidase

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

**The first step towards knowledge is to
know that we are ignorant
--Richard Cecil**

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

Mango (*Mangifera indica* L.) belongs to the family *Anacardiaceae* (order *Sapindales*), occupies paramount place among the fruit crops grown in India and it is christened as the “King of Fruits” and “National Fruit of India” owing to its delicious flavour and taste. The genus *Mangifera* is believed to have originated in Indo-Burma region (Vavilov, 1926) during the *Eocene* or an earlier period in the *Cretaceous*, and later the species have spread to Sri Lanka in the west, and to Eastern Malaysia and the Philippines in the east (Mukherjee, 1953; Singh *et al.*, 2016). The family contains over 600 species classified into 73 genera that include other important cultivated species such as pistachio (*Pistacia vera* L.) and cashew (*Anacardium occidentale* L.). Among these 73 genera, *Mangifera* genus contains about 69 species, which are mostly restricted to tropical Asia. The centre of diversity of this genus is thought to be South East Asia, with increased diversity in Peninsular Malaysia. The highest number of *Mangifera* species is now found in Borneo, Sumatra, Java and Malay Peninsula (Bompard and Schnell, 1997). There are more than 1,500 varieties of mango in the world of which about 1,200 are found in India. Mango is a diploid ($2n=40$) with a genome of 439 Mbp (Arumuganathan and Earle, 1991; Singh *et al.*, 2016), which is about two and a half times that of *Arabidopsis thaliana* (Bennet and Leitch, 2005).

According to NHB and FAOSTAT data, India leads in cultivation area (2.56 million ha) as well as production (19.27 million tonne) of mango which is contributing majorly to the total world production. Besides this India is also the largest exporter of fresh mango and mango pulp (Anonymous, 2014). Though efforts had been made for increasing the production and productivity during the last four decades, but the productivity of mango orchards in India is still low as 7.50 t/ha. Mango malformation disease was first reported in India in 1891 (Watt, 1891); however, it has now become a global problem.

Mango malformation is the chief problem and a serious constraint to mango production in India and other mango growing countries (tropical and subtropical) of the world (Crane and Campbell, 1994; Kumar *et al.*, 2011). This disease is widespread in

flowers and vegetative shoots of mango. It has a crippling effect on mango production (Hiffny *et al.*, 1978) bringing in heavy economic losses. It is estimated that in India, it causes approximately 50-80 per cent losses every year (Kumar and Chakrabarti, 1997) and cause gross deformations of vegetative and floral tissues in mango (Ploetz, 2001). In the past, breeding approaches have been utilized to overcome the mango malformation to get high yield and quality fruits. Several fungi are associated with mango malformation disease (MMD), all of which are in the *Gibberella fujikurai* species complex (*i.e.*, *F. subglutinans* sensu lato). The etiology of malformation remains debatable, and various biotic and abiotic factors, including viruses, mites, and nutritional deficiencies (Chakrabarti, 2011; Gamliel-Atinsky, 2010), have been reported to cause this disease. However, evidence has indicated the involvement of fungus as a causal organism of this malformation (Chakrabarti, 2011; Kvas *et al.* 2008; Gamliel-Atinsky, 2009a; Nor *et al.* 2013). Several members of the genus *Fusarium*, including *F. mangiferae* (previously identified as *F. moniliforme* and later as *F. moniliforme* var. *subglutinans*), *F. mexicanum*, *F. sterilihyphosum*, *F. proliferatum*, *F. subglutinans*, *F. pseudocircinatum*, and *F. tupsiense*, are associated with this disease (Youssef *et al.*, 2007) with *F. mangiferae* being the major causal agent in most countries (Crespo *et al.*, 2012; Nor *et al.*, 2013; Freeman *et al.*, 2014; Marasas *et al.*, 2006; Gamliel-Atinsky *et al.*, 2009b, Zhan *et al.*, 2010; Otero-Colina *et al.*, 2010; Lima *et al.*, 2012; Lv *et al.*, 2013, Sinniah *et al.*, 2013, Liu *et al.*, 2016b) Pathogenic organisms are capable of substantially altering hormonal activities in cells (Pusztahelyi *et al.*, 2015). During the developmental process of bud to panicle, plant undergoes highly different biochemical and physiological changes in gene expression profiles. These differences provide an ingenious system to discover molecular mechanisms and genes for mango malformation.

Fusarium having high variability and diverse distribution in various habitats so corresponding resistance genes also having high polymorphism with commonly clustered in genome. The conventional breeding approaches for developing *Fusarium* disease resistant varieties are slow in progress due to complex nature. So to overcome this, *in-silico* analysis study can be a very promising approach (Dutt, *et al.*, 2010; Mallikarjuna *et al.*, 2016; Bhati *et al.*, 2016; Azam *et al.*, 2017).

The *in-silico* analysis can be performed by using DNA and protein sequences of various *Fusarium* species available at NCBI database for better understanding of plant defences against various biotic stresses, identification of resistant genes (protein's structure and function), and resistance gene analogs (RGAs), genetic mapping, synteny analysis and also can be used for development of markers for molecular breeding.

In present era, transcriptomic study revealed several novel outcomes from the interaction of plants and pathogen (Caldo *et al.*, 2006). In plant breeding resistance genes play crucial role in specific immune response along with activation of plant defense mechanisms (Barbosa-da-Silva, 2005). Plants protect themselves against severe pathogens by basal defense mechanism (also called innate immune system). Defense mechanisms in the fruit crop trees are mainly complex and composed of multilayers of defense which are effective for diverse group of pathogens (Bari and Jones, 2009). However, various inducible defense *i.e.* molecular, biochemical, and morphological changes, synthesis of antimicrobial compounds, expression of defense genes, PCD (Programmed cell death), and oxidative burst mechanisms which are triggered upon pathogen attack/infection (Van Loon *et al.* 2006). Transcriptome analysis in healthy and malformed tissue will be helpful in understanding the molecular mechanism by discovering of important defense related genes. The study will be helpful in identification of resistant gene against *Fusarium mangiferae* and mango breeding program to solve the world wide problem of mango malformation.

More importantly during panicle development stage, gene expression profiles have not been investigated. The next-generation sequencing (NGS) technologies offer unique opportunities for genomics and functional genomics research of economically important traits. RNA-Seq technology, which is based on deep-sequencing, enables more precise quantification of genome-wide transcript levels than previous, microarray-based methods (Wang *et al.*, 2009). However, little is known about the actual transcriptional changes and their regulation during the pathogen-plant interaction. Understanding the underlying changes during this interaction would allow for the identification of signal transduction pathways affected by infection and the interaction mechanisms during infection, which can lead to improvement and understanding the regulatory networks of key biological processes in mango malformation.

A gene regulatory network (GRN's) plays a decisive role in every stage of life, along with cell differentiation, cell cycle, metabolism and signal transduction (Karlebach and Shamir, 2008; Bernot *et al.*, 2013). GRN's helps in better understanding of biological processes, mainly due to the high-throughput data obtained from interactomics, transcriptomics and microarray. The formation of gene networks from transcriptomic data helps in understanding of functional interactions among genes. Therefore their possible functions could be assigned to genes having unknown function on the basis of interactions among genes of known functions (Lopez *et al.*, 2013).

The protein-protein interaction will play a crucial role in unravelling the complex problems in plants and will also helpful in predicting the function of unknown protein (Fukao, 2012). Mostly 80 per cent of the proteins rarely execute their biological functions separately, but execute in the complex forms (Berggard *et al.*, 2007) and these complex form can only studied through PPI networks (Rual *et al.*, 2005). The protein-protein interaction can be detected by high-throughput techniques *i.e. in-silico* (ortholog-based sequence approach, domain-pairs-based sequence approach, structure-based approaches, gene neighborhood, gene fusion, I2H, phylogenetic tree, gene expression) *in-vivo* (Y2H, synthetic lethality) and *in-vitro* (TAP-MS, affinity chromatography, co-immuno precipitation, Protein microarrays, phage display, X-ray crystallography and NMR spectroscopy). PPI's provides a better understanding of biological process (interaction between cells, homeostasis, biotic and abiotic stresses, plant defense and organ formation), molecular process (phosphorylation, recruitment of transcriptional co-factor, enzyme PTM for activation or deactivation and transporter activation), physiological, developmental and pathological process in the plants (von Mering *et al.*, 2002; Uhrig, 2006). The PPI's network is mainly depends on the physical interaction between the proteins in which physical interaction are depicted as edge and proteins by dots. The knowledge regarding the dynamics of protein-protein interaction will help in completion of biotechnological projects quickly and cheaply compare to wet lab analysis.

In order to prevent mango malformation, the most economical and fundamental pathway is to breed disease-resistant varieties, because chemical control is not the permanent solution. The discovery of defense mechanism is a prerequisite for disease control through molecular breeding. Therefore to understand the pathogenic mechanism of mango

malformation the present study will provide a scientific basis to develop effective measures to control disease.

Keeping above usefulness in mind, present study was undertaken with the following objectives:

Objectives:

1. To study the differential expression of transcripts in malformed and healthy tissues.
2. To identify the functional annotations, pathway and gene networks of the DEGs.

CHAPTER II

**REVIEW
OF
LITERATURE**

**Learn, but learn from learned
-Cato**

Mango malformation, a serious fungal disease caused by *Fusarium mangiferae* which results in the great loss to mango industry not only in India but also in the other mango growing parts of the world. It was first reported in the Darbhanga district of Bihar by Watt (1891) and from there it extended to the other parts of the world such as Middle east (Hassan, 1944), Egypt (Attiah, 1955), Pakistan (Khan and Khan, 1960), South Africa (Schwartz, 1968), Brazil (Flechtmann et al., 1970), Sudan (Minessey et al., 1971), Israel and Mexico (Malo and McMillan, 1972), Cuba (Padron, 1983), United Arab Emirates (Burhan, 1991), Bangladesh (Meah and Khan, 1992), Australia (Issarakraisila et al., 1997), United States of America (Marasas et al., 2006), Sultanate of Oman (Kvas et al., 2008), Southern Spain (Crespo et al., 2012).

According to Kumar et al. (2014) many of the *Fusarium* species responsible for the cause of this disease are *Fusarium mangiferae* (Summanwar et al., 1966; Zhan et al., 2012; Joshi et al., 2014), *F. sterilihyphosum* (Lima et al., 2009; Marasas et al., 2006), *F. mexicanum* (Rodriguez-Alvarado et al., 2008; Otero-Colina et al., 2010), *F. proliferatum* (Nor et al., 2013), *F. oxysporum* (Bhatnagar and Beniwal, 1977), *F. subglutinans* (Steenkamp et al., 2000; Lima et al., 2009), *F. nivale* (Khaskheli et al., 2008, Lima et al., 2009), *F. culmorum*, *F. nygamai*, *F. pseudonygamai*, *F. nelsonii* (Wafaa et al., 2010), *F. parvisorum*, *F. incarnatum* (Liew et al., 2013), *F. scirpi* (Liew et al., 2016), *F. verticillioides* (Wafaa et al., 2010; Liew et al., 2013), *F. tuiense* (Senghor et al., 2016) and *F. pseudocircinatum* (Garcia-Lopez et al., 2016). In the recent past the disease had destroyed several mango orchards not only in India but also worldwide. The average yield loss due to malformation is 50-60 per cent and during critical conditions it may cause up to 100 per cent also. However its susceptibility vary not only from variety to variety but also from tree to tree (Misra et al., 2000).

Over more than 125 years of research has been performed on several aspects of mango malformation that include causal agent, detection of pathogen and its occurrence, genetic diversity, cytology, life cycle, chemical control measure, cultural practices, bio-pesticides, intensity of malformation, varietal susceptibility and resistance, resistant

breeding, hormonal levels (auxin, GA, cytokinin, ABA and ethylene) nutritional aspects (macro and micronutrient), physiological aspects (photosynthesis, respiration, stomatal conductance, stomatal resistance and transpiration) biochemical aspects (carbohydrate, nucleic acid, protein, amino acid and phenolic acid) and molecular marker studies has been carried out. But no single commercial variety has been developed which is having commercial fruit yield characters with complete resistance to mango malformation.

In present era, RNA-seq technique is most commonly used for finding out the host-pathogen interaction in several crop plants like banana and *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *cubense* (Li *et al.*, 2013), soybean and *F. oxysporum* (Lanubile *et al.*, 2014), tomato-*Xanthomonas perforans* race T3 (Du *et al.*, 2015), pea and *Phytophthora pisi* (Hosseini *et al.*, 2015), wheat and *Heterodera avenae* (Kong *et al.*, 2015), and oil palm and *Ganoderma* spp. (Ho *et al.*, 2016). RNA seq technology had helped in identification of several genes which were involved in defense mechanisms and resistance to different diseases. However by using the modern molecular biological and biotechnological techniques like RNA-seq, which can lead to new insights into malformation disease resistance by understanding the host-pathogen interactions. Due to dearth of knowledge on host pathogen interactions, here we cited review of literature on various crops to have a better understanding of interaction as well as basic defense mechanisms which play crucial roles in disease resistance.

De-novo assembly

De-novo characterization of the banana root under *Fusarium oxysporum* infection was achieved using CAP3 SAS (sequence assembly software) by Wang *et al.* (2012). Deep-sequencing of cDNA resulted in 26,662,006 sequence reads including single-end reads and paired-end reads having length of 90 bp each which produced approximately 2.39 Gbp of raw data. In the banana root transcriptome total base pairs, average read length, mean length of scaffolds, total number of scaffolds (>100bp) and longest scaffold length are 2,399,580,540 bp, 90 bp, 1439 bp, 25,158 and 12,963 respectively. In the data most of (90%) distinct gene sequences were unique. In oil palm transcriptome, the per cent reads (Nos.) were 3.1%, 0.9% and 2.4% for *Ganoderma* sp. 10597 SS1, *Trichoderma harzianum* CBS226.95, *Trichoderma virens* Gv29-8 and

Trichoderma reesei were observed by Ho *et al.* (2016). They observed 13 per cent of protein coding sequences belonging to fungi have high similarity to the NR database (protein) at NCBI. The reads belonging to unigenes were 5.8%, 0.4% and 0.3% in G-treated, T-treated and untreated roots of oil palm.

Liu *et al.* (2016b) studied the transcriptomic study in mango and *Fusarium mangiferae*, which resulted a total of 99,410,732 reads for all four libraries which were taken in consideration for the *de-novo* assembly whereas, total nucleotide, Q20 percentage and GC percentage of four sample were 9,941,073,200, 98.28% and 48.27% respectively. The reliable reads of 200-3000 bp were grouped (assembled) into 133,077 contigs which on clustering revealed 121,267 unigenes with a N50 of 1222 bp.

GC content analysis

The functioning of genome, gene regulation and species ecology are significantly affected due to the GC content. It also plays crucial role in the evolutionary process of plants. In monocot it vary from 33.6% to 48.9%. It has been observed that higher the GC content in plants better will be the adaptation against desiccation and cell freezing stress in plants (Smarda *et al.*, 2014).

In unripe and mid-ripe fruit of *Mangifera indica* (var. Dashehari) transcriptome, Srivastava *et al.* (2016) observed the GC content which varied from 49 (unripe fruit) to 51 per cent (ripe fruit) in raw reads, while in trimmed reads it varied from 44.33 (ripe fruit) to 45 per cent. Liu *et al.* (2016b) observed 48.26 per cent GC content in the *Fusarium mangiferae* infected transcriptome of Keitt variety of mango. The average GC content was analysed by Bhadauria *et al.* (2017) in transcriptome of lentil infected with *Colletotrichum lentil*. They observed 54.9 per cent GC content in fungal unigenes whereas the average GC content in unigenes of lentil was 39.64 per cent.

Functional Annotation

Wang *et al.* (2012) used BLASTx for annotation of 25,158 distinct gene sequences in banana root transcriptome using NR database, GO, and the KEGG database with a cutoff E-value of 10^{-5} . Among all distinct gene sequences, 85.94% (21,622) returned a valid BLAST result, whereas 40% (3,536) of the distinct gene

sequences couldn't be annotated. In Banana, analysis of defense related genes was carried out by Li *et al.*, (2012) to have better insight into the molecular biology. Total 5008 defense related unigenes were present in banana transcriptome enriched in various relevant resistant pathways indicating their conservation in banana and other different plants and will be helpful in both local and systemic acquired resistance. The defense related genes were classified in different categories *i.e.* PAMPs (1409), plant hormones biosynthesis and signalling (643), transcription factors (588), cell wall modification (574), ion fluxes (294), flavonoid (377), oxidative burst (288), effector-triggered immunity (247), programmed cell death (178), plant pathogenesis-related proteins (74) and G-proteins (124).

Wu *et al.* (2014) studied the transcriptome and proteomic analysis of fruits of mango *cv.* 'Zill' and observed 78.43% transcripts annotated with NR database followed by 48.67% with Swiss-Prot and 26.97% were aligned with COG database. *Vitis vinifera* had highest (29.9%) top hit matches followed by *Ricinus communis* (27.6%), *Populus trichocarpa* (22.9%), *Glycine max* (6.3%), *Medicago truncatula* (1.8%), *Arabidopsis lyrata* subsp. *lyrata* (1.2%) and *Arabidopsis thaliana* (1.1%). Azim *et al.* (2014) performed the annotation and classification of unigenes from mango transcriptome through BLASTN against the NR database and out of 30,509 unigenes, the BLAST search results revealed the annotation of 80% unigenes (24,593). The CDS in mango unigenes were BLASTN against the genomic sequence datasets of several Viriplantae species. Maximum (37%) matches were found with sweet orange followed by black cottonwood (22.5%), grapevine (18.3%), castor bean (17.9%), soybean (17.3%), barrel medic (10.5%) and arabidopsis (6.7%) whereas 10.4% of sequences matched with other species sequences. A study was carried out on *de-novo* assembly of mango fruit peel transcriptome by Luria *et al.* (2014) for similar sequence search against NR database. The unigenes sequences had 62.07% (35,917) transcript annotated. Among them 53.12% had high homology (E-value <10⁻⁶⁰) while 20.9% showed results with high homology (10⁻⁶⁰ < E-value <10⁻³⁰). The top hit among the species showed maximum (35.9%) similarity with *Theobroma cacao* followed by *Vitis vinifera* (14.2%), *Ricinus communis* (12.1%) and *Populus trichocarpa* (12%) while minimum was observed with

Prunus persica (7.5%), *Fragaria vesca* (2.3%), *Glycine max* (2.2%) and *Cucumis sativus* (1.8%).

The *de-novo* transcriptome assembly of mango cv. Kent fruit mesocarp was used for annotation of the sequences through Swiss-Prot and NCBI non-redundant by Dautt-Castro *et al.* (2015). According to NR database, 98.2% (32,650) deduced proteins had significant BLASTp match with amino acid sequences present in NR database; whereas unigenes sequence blasted with Swiss-Prot database showed 25,154 unigenes fully annotated and 3,905 unigenes were partially annotated. Out of 33,142 protein sequences the top hit with different species revealed maximum (12,249, 36.9%) similarity with *Citrus sinensis* followed by *Citrus clementina* (11,708, 35.3%). A similarity searches against three different protein databases i.e. 'Gene Bank', 'TAIR', and 'Uni-Prot' was carried out by Sherman *et al.* (2015). Functional annotation of pool transcriptome of mango cultivar Tommy Atkins and Keitt resulted into 85% hits (40,971).

Liu *et al.* (2016b) studied the transcription profiling analysis of mango cv. Keitt and *Fusarium mangiferae* interaction. They aligned unigenes sequences by using BLASTX with four protein database and total 75,802 (62.51%) unigenes were annotated. The maximum annotation (60.62%) was found in NR database while Swiss-Prot had 46.88%, KEGG had 23.83% and least was observed in COG (19.72%). The top matches in species were found with *Theobroma cacao* (32.23%) followed by *Vitis vinifera* (14.62%), *Cucumis sativus* (5.60%), *Fragaria vesca* subsp. *vesca* (5.34%), *Arabidopsis thaliana* (3.87%), *Cicer arietinum* (3.64%), *Glycine max* (3.46%) and *Oryza sativa Japonica Group* (3.22%). The total transcripts of cultivar Dashehari when blasted against two databases i.e. UniProt and NR, by Srivastava *et al.* (2016) revealed annotation of 34,934 and 44,472 genes respectively. The top five hits were found with *Citrus sinensis* followed by *Citrus clementia*, *Theobroma cacao*, *Arabidopsis thaliana* and *Vitis vinifera*. To annotate the unigenes in *Mangifera indica* L. cv. Zill, Hong *et al.* (2016) studied the transcriptome of mango fruit against *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides* and searched the unigenes sequence against six different databases i.e. NR, KEGG, Swiss-Prot, InterPro, COG and Nt databases. A total 70.8% unigenes (93,325) were annotated whereas 29.2% (38,425) were not annotated to any database indicating the novelty in the genes. Among six different databases the percentage of unigenes

annotated showed maximum (67.6%) matches with NR database followed by KEGG (66.1%), Nt (64.4%), Swiss-Prot (46.8%), InterPro (42.9%) and COG (26.7%) databases.

GO analysis

In banana transcriptome 69.72% unigenes were assigned 10,428 GO terms with 45 GO sub-categories (Wang *et al.*, 2012). The majority (4,157, 23.7%) of the GO annotations were in the cellular component category, followed by the biological process category (3,701, 21.1%), and molecular function category (9,682, 55.2%). The cellular component subcategories mainly consist of “cell”, “cell part”, “organelle”, and “organelle part” and in biological process, “metabolic process”, “cellular process”, “metabolic process”, and “response stimulus” were prominent, whereas in molecular functions “binding” and “catalytic” were two major subcategories. Bai *et al.* (2013) studied the GO analysis of *Fusarium oxysporum* infected and resistance banana root transcriptome. The total 43,305 unigenes were grouped in 59 functional categories. In biological process, ‘cellular process and metabolic process’, under molecular function ‘binding and catalytic activity’ were dominant whereas in cellular component ‘cell, cell part, and organelle’ were the most prominent categories.

Guo *et al.* (2014) studied the GO analysis in transcriptome of vascular wilt disease affected banana and he observed that most upregulated unigenes in biological process were “cellular process” (661), “nitrogen compound metabolic process” (215), “biosynthetic process” (213) and “transport” (210) were predominant. In cellular component, “membrane”, “cell part”, “integral to membrane” and “membrane part” were prominent. The down-regulated genes under gene ontology annotated in GO categories were “catalytic activity” and “metabolic process”, followed by “primary metabolic process”, “cellular metabolic process”, “nitrogen compound metabolic process” and “biosynthetic process”. Host (Mango) and pathogen (*Fusarium mangiferae*) interaction study was carried out by Liu *et al.* (2016b) through transcriptomic profiling approach. GO analysis of 36,481 gene were categorized into three classes *i.e.* biological process, cellular component and molecular function. After inoculating the *F. mangiferae* in mango, under biological process the most commonly enriched GO terms in three treatments (CK-_{VS}-45D, CK-_{VS}-75D and CK-_{VS}-120D) were

“transcription, DNA-dependent”, “protein modification process”, “gene expression”, “phosphate-containing compound metabolic process”, “developmental process involved in reproduction”, “single-organism cellular process”, “response to stress”, “primary metabolic process” and “response to hormone stimulus”.

Giampetruzzi *et al.*, (2016) performed the transcriptome analysis of two olive cultivars (Leccino and Ogliarola salentina) which were infected by the *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. Pauca (*Polyphagous bacterium*). For identification of genes and pathways related to Xfp infection, 20,668 transcripts were found hit (BLASTX search) out of 22,373 transcripts revealing 5,901 GO terms. The major categories under cellular components were “membrane”, “integral component of membrane”, “intrinsic component of membrane” and “membrane part” indicating their role in the cell wall components in the signalling response against Xfp whereas “catalytic activity” was most prominent category under molecular function.

KEGG pathways

KEGG (<http://www.kegg.jp/>) is a confederate database which is used for biological elucidation of genome sequences and other high-throughput data obtained through genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics and metabolomics (Kanehisa *et al.*, 2016). In the field of bioinformatics, KEGG serve as important reservoir of information for connecting genomes to life as well as the environment. The database mainly consist of molecular functions, reaction, and interactions of genes and proteins associated with orthologs specific to particular organisms. KEGG pathway mapping is procedure in which biological system are represented through computer in which genomic information (consisting of molecular building blocks of genes), chemical information (proteins and chemical substances) and systems information (knowledge on molecular wiring diagrams of interaction, reaction and relation networks) are generated.

Biological pathways which were active in mango were identified by Liu *et al.* (2016) through mapping the annotated sequence to the reference pathways in Kyoto Encyclopaedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) database. The maximum number of unigenes (1716, 7.18%) were assigned to “ribosome” followed by 862 in “oxidative phosphorylation” (3.6%) and 854 in “protein processing in endoplasmic reticulum”

(3.57%). To identify the KEGG pathways which were more active in *Fusarium oxysporum* infected and resistant roots of banana transcriptome, Bai *et al.* (2013) mapped 59,340 unigenes sequences to the reference canonical pathways in, KEGG database. Out of the total unigene sequences mapped, 35,313 unigenes were assigned into 127 KEGG pathways. The maximum number of unigenes (24.77%) were categorized into ‘metabolic pathway’ followed by ‘biosynthesis of secondary metabolites’ (8.70%), ‘plant hormone signal transduction’ (7.63%), ‘endocytosis’ (7.61%), ‘plant-pathogen interaction’ (7.30%).

In banana root transcriptome under *Fusarium oxysporum* infection, 46.15% (11,611) of distinct gene sequences were functionally annotated to 192 KEGG pathways by Wang *et al.* (2012). Most of the unigene sequences were annotated to carbohydrate metabolism (1,448) followed by amino acid metabolism (978), signal transduction (921), and cell growth and death (787). According to Tan *et al.* (2015), a total of 290 differentially expressed genes were assigned to 87 KEGG pathways in transcriptome of tomato affected with *Verticillium dahliae*. The number of unigenes percent *i.e.* 10, 8.62, 8.28, 5.17, 5.17 and 5.17 were observed under phenylalanine metabolism and phenylpropanoid biosynthesis, plant hormone signal transduction, plant–pathogen interaction, cysteine and methionine metabolism, protein processing in endoplasmic reticulum and oxidative phosphorylation pathways respectively.

COG analysis

The annotation of data to COGs (clusters of orthologous groups of proteins) database is a process of phylogenetic classification of the proteins encoded in complete genomes. The COG database mainly consist of both prokaryotic clusters (COGs) and eukaryotic clusters (KOGs). The formation of clusters of orthologous groups of proteins involves an automatic procedure for estimation of candidate sets of orthologs followed by splitting of multifarious domain proteins into the component domains manually and thereafter subsequent manual curation and annotation. In computational genomics, COGNITOR program is widely used for COGs analysis. The COGs had valuable applications in terms of functional annotation of newly sequenced genomes (Natale *et al.*, 2001) and finding the genome-wide evolutionary pattern (Jordan *et al.*, 2002). Beside these, it also helps in evaluating the whole of the transcriptome library for

annotation process and thereafter all the annotated unigenes were aligned to the COG database to predict and classify possible functions.

Bai *et al.* (2013) annotated 20,713 unigenes sequences from *Fusarium* infected banana transcriptome with COG database which was further classified into 25 COG categories. The top COG category in which maximum number of unigenes were annotated are ‘general function prediction’ (7,573), ‘transcription’ (6053), ‘replication, recombination and repair’ (4506), and ‘signal transduction mechanisms’ (4223) while least number of unigenes were annotated in ‘nuclear structure’ (5) and ‘extracellular structures’ (17).

A study on COG analysis with 862 differentially expressed genes was carried out by Tan *et al.*, (2015), on transcriptome of tomato infected with *Verticillium dahlia* using RNA-Seq approach. The total 642 unigenes annotated by COG analysis were grouped into 20 functional categories. Most number of unigenes (104) were assigned into “general function prediction only” followed by “posttranslational modification, protein turnover, chaperones”, “secondary metabolites biosynthesis, transport and catabolism” (70), “amino acid transport and metabolism” (57), “carbohydrate transport and metabolism” (43), “energy production and conversion” (41), “function unknown” (38), “inorganic ion transport and metabolism” (34), “lipid transport and metabolism” (31), “defense mechanisms” (23), “signal transduction mechanisms” (21) whereas least number of unigenes categories were annotated into “RNA processing and modification”, “cytoskeleton”, “replication, recombination and repair” and “nucleotide transport and metabolism”.

Plant pathogen interaction

Kong *et al.* (2015) observed 26 differentially expressed genes related to plant pathogen interaction pathways in transcriptome of cucumber infected *Botrytis cinerea*. Out of 26 DEG’s, 18 were upregulated (RBOH, CERK, CNGC, BAK, MEKK1, WRKY2-33 and JAZ), 8 were downregulated (NOS, PR-1 and HSP) and two genes (CDPK and CaMCML) showed both up and down-regulated pattern. The most prominent disease resistance gene categories observed in plant pathogen interaction pathways on transcriptome analysis of *Oryza meyeriana*, revealed FLS2 (Flagellin receptor), EF-Tu (Elongation factor-Tu receptor), CNGC (cyclic nucleotide gated

channel), CaMCML (calcium-binding protein CML), RIN4 (RPM1-interacting protein 4), CDPK (calcium-dependent protein kinase), RPM1 (disease resistance protein RPM1), SGT1 (suppressor of G2 allele of SKP1) and HSP90 (heat shock protein) (He *et al.*, 2015). Transcriptome analysis of wild rice (*Oryza meyeriana*) infected with *Xanthomonas oryzae pv. Oryzae* revealed 19 DEGs belonging to 133 DEUs in the plant-pathogen interaction pathways. In two immune signalling pathways *i.e.* PTI (PAMP triggered immunity) and ETI (effector-triggered immunity), 16 DEGs were enriched (Cheng *et al.*, 2016). The genes which were up-regulated in plant pathogen interaction network pathway were CPK, RBOH, MKK4/5P, MKK1/2, WRKY22/29, WRKY25/33, RIN4, RPM1, PBS-1 and HSP90 whereas, down-regulated genes were NOS, MEKK1, RIN4, HSP90 and PBS-1.

After inoculation of *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* in soybean, Yuan *et al.* (2017) studied the differentially expressed genes in plant-pathogen interaction pathways (KO: 04626) at five different development stages (branching stage, flowering stage, fruiting stage, pod stage, and harvest stage). They observed 24 categories of genes, which were significantly expressed. Among differentially expressed genes, MAPK kinase (MKK4/5), coronatine-insensitive protein 1 (COI1), jasmonate ZIM domain-containing protein (JAZ), elongation factor Tu 18 (elf18), pathogenesis-related protein 1 (PR1), chitin elicitor-binding protein (CEBiP) were the most prominent categories in plant-pathogen interaction pathways of soybean. They found that these genes in soybean symbiotic process regulate the nodule development along with host soybean immunity defense. The study on plant-pathogen interaction pathways in the resistant and susceptible tomato lines on *Xanthomonas perforans* Race T3 infection revealed 16 defence response genes (Du *et al.*, 2015). The defense genes observed were CPK (calcium dependent protein kinase), CNGF (cyclic nucleotide gated channel), CALM (calmodulin), CML (calcium binding protein CML), WRKY 33, HSP90 (heat Shock Protein), JAZ (jasmonate ZIM domain-containing protein).

Phenylpropanoid biosynthesis pathway

Phenylpropanoids (lignins, flavonols, isoflavonoids, and anthocyanins) are a myriad group of compounds which are physiologically active secondary metabolites

(SMs) produced by various biotic and abiotic stresses and those stress related phenylpropanoids compounds are termed as phytoalexins (Vogt, 2010). Phenylpropanoid biosynthesis pathways consist of complex series of biochemical reaction leading to the formation of secondary metabolites or phenolic compounds and these natural products of pathways lead to biotic and abiotic stress stimulus by transcriptional activation of the various biosynthetic pathway genes (La Camera *et al.*, 2004). The natural phenylpropanoid products play crucial roles in the form of signaling molecules that result into plant growth and development and disease resistance. When resistant plants are attack by pathogen, there is rapid accumulation of phenolic compounds that prevent the site of infection from pathogen (Cherif *et al.*, 2007).

The phenolics which occur constitutively and behaves as inhibitors are known as phytoanticipins whereas phenolics which are produced after pathogen attack resulting in active defense are known as phytoalexins. During incompatible and compatible plant-pathogen interactions, phytoalexins plays important roles in host's resistance specificity (Barz *et al.*, 1990). After the pathogen attack, the antimicrobial compound synthesised in plants are pterocarpans (e.g., glyceollin), isoflavans, prenylated isoflavonoids (e.g., kievitone), stilbenes, psoralens, coumarins, 3-deoxyanthocyanidins, flavonols (e.g., quercetin, kaempferol), and auronones (Dixon *et al.*, 2002). The secondary metabolic pathways *i.e.* phenylpropanoid biosynthesis pathway plays a crucial role in plant defense and also serve as rich source of metabolites in plants which leads to formation of other different compounds *i.e.* coumarins, flavonoids and lignans (Fraser and Chapple, 2011).

Wang *et al.* (2012) studied the phenylpropanoid biosynthesis pathways in the transcriptome of *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. cubense tropical race 4 infected banana and they found that after 2 DPI, 21 enzymes were enriched belonging to 17 peroxidases and four 4-coumarate:one coenzyme a ligases, two cinnamate 4-hydroxylases and one phenylalanine ammonia lyase. Transcriptome and expression analysis of resistant and susceptible banana infected with *Fusarium oxysporum* indicated that in resistant cultivar Yueyoukang-1, phenylpropanoid biosynthesis pathways were highly enriched at all of the five infection stages along with three other pathways *i.e.* metabolic pathways, biosynthesis of secondary metabolites and RNA transport. During all five stages of infection, they also observed three common pathways *i.e.* metabolic pathways,

phenylpropanoid biosynthesis and phenylalanine metabolism which were significantly enriched in the susceptible cultivar Brazilian. After 5 and 10 DPI, DEGs in the phenylpropanoid biosynthesis varied from 31 to 37 while it varied from 15 to 45 during 0.5, 3 and 10 DPI (Bai *et al.*, 2013). Similarly in near isogenic lines of maize transcriptome resistance to *Fusarium graminearum*, Liu *et al.* (2016a) observed three genes namely PALs (phenylalanine ammonia-lyases), C4H (cinnamate-4-hydroxylase), and 4CL2 (4-coumarate-CoA ligase 2), that were significantly induced. In the phenylpropanoid biosynthesis pathways of mango malformation transcriptome infected with *Fusarium mangiferae*, Liu *et al.* (2016b) observed 34 differentially expressed genes. Among them 25 genes were up-regulated and nine genes were down-regulated. The differentially expressed genes were peroxidases (8), alcohol dehydrogenases (6), cinnamyl alcohol dehydrogenases (6) catalase-peroxidases (4).

Biosynthesis of secondary metabolite

Secondary metabolites (SMs) are the low molecular weight organic compounds (molecular mass < 3000 Ds) which are not involved in plant growth and development like primary metabolite (Andersson, 2012; Scharf *et al.*, 2014). The fungi and plant are abundant source of SMs which are mainly classified into three classes *i.e.* terpenes (monoterpenes, sesquiterpenes, diterpenes, triterpenes, and polyterpenes) nitrogen containing compounds (alkaloids, cyanogenic glucosides, and non-protein amino acids), phenolic compounds (coumarin, furano-coumarins, lignin, flavonoids, isoflavonoids, and tanins), and sulphur containing secondary metabolites such as GSH, GSL, phytoalexins, thionins, defensins and allinin (Mazid *et al.*, 2011). The SMs produced by fungi act as antifungal, antiviral, antibacterial and anti-tumour (Keller *et al.*, 2005). Besides this, they play crucial roles in diverse biological activities (reduction in disease infection, prevent the pathogen invading, increase shelf life of plant and attracting the pollinators) and applications (pharmaceutical, production of insecticide, pesticide, antibiotics and colouring agents). Their production in plants after pathogen attack is positively correlated with the disease resistance and also varies according to genera to genera and species to species. The biosynthesis of secondary metabolite pathways were significantly enriched after pathogen attack in banana infected with *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. cubense Tropical Race 4 (Li *et al.*, 2012; Bai *et al.*, 2013), *Fusarium*

verticillioides infected maize genotypes (Lanubile *et al.*, 2014) and mango infected with *Fusarium mangiferae* (Liu *et al.*, 2016b),

Transcription factors

Plant transcription factors are the proteins that act in combination with other transcriptional regulators which include chromatin remodelling or modification in the proteins to involve or stop RNA polymerases to the DNA template (Udvardi *et al.*, 2007). Normally seven per cent of coding sequences in plant genome are assigned to transcription factors. The change the expression of genes from down-regulated to up-regulated is the outcome of interaction of transcription factor along with the CRE's in stress related genes which provide tolerance against abiotic stresses (Agarwal and Jha, 2010). It has been reported that DREB transcription factor plays a crucial role in resistance against pathogen attack (Agarwal *et al.*, 2006); whereas WRKY33 is responsible for resistance to necrotrophic fungal pathogens (Zheng *et al.*, 2006). The transcription factor TGA plays an important role in the regulation of PR (pathogenesis related) genes and defence response (Kesarwani *et al.*, 2007).

Wang *et al.* (2012) studied the *Fusarium oxysporum* infected banana root transcriptome and found that between highly resistant (Yueyoukang-1) and susceptible (Brazilian) cultivar three types of transcription factor 22, 33 and DREB protein were differentially expressed. They observed that at two point's time, two WRKY22 genes were up-regulated and one was down-regulated in the resistant cultivar Yueyoukang-1, whereas in susceptible cultivars, no WRKY22 genes were significantly up-regulated until 5 DPI. In addition to this, transcription factor WRKY33, TGA transcription factor and DREB protein were highly expressed in the resistant cultivar Yueyoukang-1 compared to susceptible cultivar Brazilian. The differentially expressed categories of transcription factors in citrus fruit transcriptome in response to HLB disease are AP2-EREBP, helix-loop-helix, bZIP, C2H2, zinc finger, C2C2-CO-like, MYB related, WRKY, and AS2 gene families (Martinelli *et al.*, 2012). The banana transcriptome of susceptible and resistant roots with *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. cubense tropical race 4 was studied by Bai *et al.*, (2013). Between the two cultivars namely Yueyoukang-1 and

Brazilian, they observed different expression pattern of the three TF's (WRKY-TF 22, WRKY TF 33 and DREB protein).

Flowering genes

Flowering is a complex development stage involving several physiological and morphological changes which are governed by several exogenous and endogenous cues (Hanke *et al.*, 2007; Higgins *et al.*, 2010). The ultimate reproductive success and survival of the tree mainly depends on the flowering behaviour of the tree. Mango malformation disease is also related to the flowering. Therefore, it becomes necessary to know the different flowering genes from flower bud to panicle development. However, it becomes a challenging process for identification and molecular characterization of flowering genes due to complex and large genomes size of mango. In leaf transcriptome of *Lagerstroemia indica*, Zhang *et al.* (2014) identified flowering related genes. They observed 115 genes related to flowering time and out of these genes, 75 were categorized into four flowering pathways *i.e.* photoperiod, vernalization, autonomous, and GA. The number of unigenes in four different flowering pathways namely photoperiod, vernalization, autonomous and GA pathways were 34, 17, 12 and 12 unigenes respectively. According to Li *et al.*, (2017) transcription factor genes also play an important role in regulation of flower development in *Taihangia rupestris*. They identified stress related transcription factor namely NAC, WRKY, bHLH, GRAS, and ERF that were highly expressed in male flowers whereas in bisexual flowers WOX, YAB, AP2, and C2H2, transcription factors were associated with flower organ development. Under drought stress condition in maize leaves, Song *et al.*, (2017) studied the transcriptome analysis of flowering genes. They observed the flowering genes related to flowering time, reproduction, interaction of pollen and pistil interaction, flower development stages and post-embryonic development. They observed that transcription factor related to drought such as HY5, CONSTANS, C2H2 zinc finger, CCCH, and NAC domains play significant roles in changing the gene expression pattern that leads to change in flowering time.

Network analysis studies

Gene regulatory network (GRN's) helps in better understanding of biological processes, mainly due to the high-throughput data obtained from interactomics, transcriptomics and microarray. The formation of gene networks from transcriptomic data helps in understanding the functional interactions among genes. Therefore their possible functions could be assigned to genes having unknown function on the basis of interactions among genes of known functions (Lopez *et al.*, 2013). Beside this gene regulatory network also are useful in understanding the genetic relationship, robustness and evolution genes. The protein-protein interaction plays crucial roles in unravelling the complex problems in plants and will also be helpful in predicting the function of unknown protein (Fukao, 2012). Mostly 80 per cent of the proteins rarely execute their biological functions separately, but execute in the complex forms (Berggard *et al.*, 2007) and these complex forms can only studied through PPI networks (Rual *et al.*, 2005).

Ding *et al.*, (2014) studied the protein-protein interaction network for different plant hormone signaling proteins of sweet orange along with *Arabidopsis* Hormone Database (AHD2.0). They observed that proteins related to different phytohormones resulted into a highly interconnected network with TOR (Target of rapamycin) in its center. TOR plays important roles in growth and development, stress tolerance/resistance and mRNA translation. They also found direct interaction of PP2A (protein phosphatase 2A) regulatory subunit and catalytic subunit along with target of rapamycin (TOR). In addition to this, several interactions were observed between signaling proteins of jasmonic and salicylic acid and most of those interactions were regulated by MPK4 and MMK1, and several of them also interact with MKK2 and MKK6; and these also directly interact with target of rapamycin (Ding *et al.*, 2014). Furthermore, TOR is also interconnected with shaggy-related protein, protein phosphatase PP1 and TRRAP (phosphatidylinositol 3-/4- kinase), BRI1 (Brassinosteroid insensitive-1), BSU, 14-3-3 protein and auxinic transporters (Ding *et al.*, 2014).

For identification of the proteins and genes involvement in bacterial blight defense, Jayaswall *et al.* (2016) analysed the interaction of defense proteins from tea transcriptome along with already determined PPI network of *Arabidopsis*. They

identified 149 defense related genes, among them 126 were successfully assigned to TAIR-IDs. Out 149 genes, 88 dense genes were mapped and having interconnection with 746 nodes and 3626 edges. In the protein-protein interaction network for each gene, the average number of undirected neighbours was approximately 9.72. The results of PPI network indicated that R-genes, defense related enzymes, transcription factors, retero-transposon, multidrug resistant category and other defense related genes were interconnected with 35, 125, 149, 175, 149 and 41 genes respectively.

Fungal transcripts

The different *Fusarium* species are extensively present in various habitats like soil, subterranean and aerial plant parts, plant detritus, and other organic substrates (Nelson *et al.*, 1994). *Fusarium* resistance genes originated through gene duplication and are continuously evolving through unequal exchange and also due to constant selection pressure by pathogen evolution (Joshi and Nayak, 2013). The fungal transcripts in treated oil palm were studied by Ho *et al.* (2016) to get the overview of fungal related gene expression. They found high number of similarity between the unigenes sequence and fungal sequences. The enzyme *i.e.* glycoside hydrolases and glycosyl transferases, cellulases and polysaccharide lyase as well as carbohydrate binding modules which were encoded by fungal transcripts were high in number whereas enzyme responsible for cell wall degrading/ modification were absent in the treated samples. Among the fungal transcripts, gene encoding phosphate transporters, sugar transporter and carbohydrate metabolism were found to be higher in number in fungal transcript.

Guo *et al.* (2014) studied the transcriptome analysis of the fungal pathogen *Fusarium oxysporum* which cause vascular wilt disease in banana. They observed the conserved orthologs in seven fungi *i.e.* *Fusarium graminearum*, *F. oxysporum* f. sp cubense race 1, *F. oxysporum* f. sp cubense race 4, *F. oxysporum* f. sp lycopersici, *F. verticillioides*, *F. solani* and *Magnaporthe grisea* (g). Out of seven fungi maximum orthologs of *F. solani* were observed followed by *F. verticillioides*, *Magnaporthe grisea*, *F. oxysporum* f. sp cubense race 1, *F. oxysporum* f. sp lycopersici and *F. oxysporum* f. sp cubense race 4 whereas least orthologs were of *Fusarium graminearum*.

CHAPTER III

MATERIALS AND METHODS

**The great invention of the world is the
invention of the method of invention
-Alfred North Whitehead**

The present study on “**Identification of genes associated with mango malformation through Differential Expression Analysis**” was carried out in Division of Fruits and Horticultural Technology, ICAR- Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi during the period 2014-15 to 2016-17. The details of material used and methodologies employed during the experimentation are described in this chapter.

3.1 GENERAL

3.1.1 Site of the experiment

The study was carried out at Division of Fruits and Horticultural Technology, ICAR-Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi which is located at 77°12’F longitude, 28°40’N latitude and having altitude of 228.6 m above mean sea level.

3.1.2 Climatic and weather conditions/ Metrological conditions

The agro-climatic conditions of IARI, New Delhi is having gangetic plains region. The climatic conditions are typical subtropical with hot and dry summer followed by cold winter. In summer the temperature varied from 41 to 44°C while in winter the minimum temperature varied from 3 to 7°C.

3.1.3 Soil

The soil structure of the experimental farm is gravelly loam to gravelly clay loam with pH ranging from 8.2 to 8.5.

3.2 EXPERIMENTAL MATERIAL

3.2.1 Plant material

Mango trees with uniform age and growth, growing at the experimental orchard, Division of Fruits and Horticulture Technology, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi were selected for the study. To study the differential expression analysis, three healthy and two malformed samples at different growth stages were collected from mango variety Amrapali, a regular bearing, dwarf and highly susceptible to mango

malformation. The five samples used for the study are as follows: single swollen malformed bud stage-1 (MB-1), multiple malformed bud stage 2 (MB-2), malformed panicle development stage-3 (MB-3), healthy bud stage-1 (HB-1) and healthy panicle development stage-2 (HB-2) (Fig.1).

3.2.2 Isolation, qualitative and quantitative analysis of total RNA

To generate transcriptome of healthy and malformed tissues of mango (*Mangifera indica* L) cultivar Amrapali, total RNA was isolated from healthy (HB-1 and HB-2) and malformed tissues (MB-1, MB-2 and MB-3) at different growth stages. Fifteen biological replicates were used to prepare one pooled RNA sample for each of the five stages. Total RNA was isolated by using Trizol method (Hongbao *et al.*, 2008). The quality of the isolated RNA was checked on 1% denatured agarose gel for the presence of 25S and 18S bands (Fig. 2a). Further, total RNA was quantified using qubit fluorometer (Annexure Table.1). Flow diagram of mango transcriptome data analysis is described in Fig. 2b.

3.2.3 Illumina NextSeq 2 x 150 PE (Pair End) library preparations

To generate the sequencing data for the malformed and healthy tissues of mango cultivar Amrapali, three cDNA libraries were constructed and subjected to Illumina deep sequencing. The paired end cDNA sequencing libraries were prepared using illumine True-Seq stranded mRNA Library preparation kit and as per its described protocol. The means of the library fragment size distributions are 504bp, 467bp, 481bp, 462bp and 480bp for MB-1, MB-2, MB-3, HB-1 and HB-2 respectively. The libraries were sequenced using 2x150PE chemistry on NextSeq-500 and 5 GB data per sample was generated. Briefly, mRNA was enriched from total RNA followed by fragmentation. The fragmented mRNA was converted into first strand cDNA, followed by second-strand generation, A-tailing, adapter ligation and finally ended by index PCR amplification of adaptor-ligated library. Library quantification and qualification was performed using DNA high sensitivity assay kit. The bio-analyzer profiles of library on agilent DNA HS chip of healthy and malformed stage is described in Fig. 3.

3.2.4 *De-novo* transcriptome assembly

The next generation sequencing for MB-1, MB-2, MB-3, HB-1 and HB-2 samples were performed using 2x150PE chemistry on the Illumina NextSeq platform and approximately 5-6 GB of data was generated per sample. Trimmomatic (V-0.30) software was used to filter Illumina reads with a Phred quality score below 20; discarding the rest of the sequence and keeping only pairs where both reads were larger than 40 bp (Bolger *et al.*, 2014). The transcripts were assembled using Bridger with default parameters. CD-Hit was run on the above mentioned Bridger (Chang *et al.*, 2015) assembled transcripts to get the unigenes. All CDS were predicted from the unigenes using Transdecoder (<http://transdecoder.sf.net>) with default parameters. The statistical elements of the assembly were calculated by in house perl scripts. The transcriptomic data of healthy and malformed tissues at different growth stages were submitted to the National Center for Biotechnology information (NCBI) (Accession numbers SAMN05727981, SAMN05727982, SAMN05727983, SAMN05727984, and SAMN05727985).

3.2.5 GC content analysis

GC content analysis of the CDS in healthy and malformed stages was determined using perl script.

3.2.6 Functional Annotation and GO Analysis

The predicted CDS were subjected to similarity search against NCBI's non-redundant (NR) database using the BLASTx algorithm. GO sequence distributions help in specifying all the annotated nodes comprising of GO functional groups. The platform independent java implementation of the Blast2GO PRO software (Gotz *et al.*, 2008) was used to retrieve associated gene ontology (GO) terms describing biological processes, molecular functions, and cellular components. CDS associated with similar functions are assigned to same GO functional group.

3.2.7 COG analysis

To further differentiate the NCBI nucleotide sequences and assembled sequences at the protein level, COG classification was undertaken to analyze the NCBI sequences.

The unigenes sequences were aligned to COG database to classify and predict possible functions.

3.2.8 KEGG pathway analysis

To identify the biological pathways in all samples, the detected CDS were mapped to reference canonical pathways in KEGG using KEGG automatic annotation server (KAAS) (Kanehisa & Goto, 2000). The mapped CDS were classified into broad categories such as metabolism, genetic information processing, environmental information processing, cellular processes and organismal system.

3.2.9 Differential Gene Expression Analysis

The DESeq package was used to detect significant differentially expressed (DE) genes between control and treated samples. Differential gene expression analysis has been carried out for commonly occurring CDS (based on common NR blast hit accession) among the control and infected samples. For differentially expressed genes, a log fold-change value $> +2$ was selected for up-regulated genes and log fold-change value < -2 was selected for down-regulated genes. To identify flowering-related genes in mango, the unigene sequences were blasted with 303 flowering genes database of *Arabidopsis thaliana*.

3.2.10 SSR (Simple Sequence Repeats) Identification

Simple sequence repeats (SSRs) or micro-satellites are the tandem repeats of nucleotide motifs of the sizes 1-6 bp and are highly polymorphic and are ubiquitously present in all the known genomes. Using the MISA software, SSR markers were identified for predicted CDS.

3.2.11 Homologous gene sequence between mango and *Fusarium* species

To identify the similarity of genes between *Fusarium* and mango (*Mangifera indica* L) during the host pathogen interactions, different species of *Fusarium* were selected and a database was developed for one to one mango transcriptome data screening.

3.2.12 Sequence retrieval of *Fusarium* resistance genes

Fusarium resistance genes of banana (*Musa acuminata*), tobacco (*Nicotiana glauca*), petunia (*Petunia x hybrid*), lily (*Lilium regale*), onion (*Allium cepa*), soybean (*Glycine max*), rice (*Oryza sativa*), arabidopsis (*Arabidopsis thaliana*), tomato (*Solanum lycopersicon*) and melon (*Cucumis melo*) were collected from NCBI (www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov) and European Nucleotide Archive (<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/data/view/<accession>>). The nucleotide and protein sequences were retrieved from NCBI, whereas coding sequences were taken from European Nucleotide Archive. The selected species comprised the representatives from ten main plant groups such as monocots, dicots and lower plants (Annexes Table.3). Flow diagram of *in-silico* analysis of *Fusarium* resistance gene are depicted in the Fig 4.

3.2.13 Secondary and tertiary structural analysis of protein sequences

The protein sequences of *Fusarium* resistance genes were used to build 3D models by the phyre2 server and were evaluated using verify-3D from PROCHECK software (Luthy *et al.*, 1992). Ramchandran plot analysis was done by Rampage. Further validation of protein structures was carried out from X-ray analysis, NMR spectroscopy and Z-score estimation was done by ProSA-web tool (Wiederstein and Sippl, 2007).

3.2.14 Binding sites and hydrophobicity analysis of protein sequence

Binding sites and hydrophobicity of five stable *Fusarium* resistance genes were predicted by phyre2 server tool (Kelley *et al.*, 2015) and for further visualization of output; PDB files were processed by discovery studio 3.5 visualizer tools.

3.2.15 Conserved domain search and trans-membrane prediction

The conserved domains among the five stable proteins were predicted through the CD-Search tool from NCBI's interface via RPS-BLAST (Marchler-Bauer *et al.*, 2014). Trans-membrane helix was predicted through TMHMM Server (trans-membrane helices hidden markov model (Krogh *et al.*, 2001) and visualization of trans-membrane helix was done by protter tool (Omasits *et al.*, 2013).

3.2.16 Multiple sequence alignment analysis, construction and visualization of Phylogenetic trees

Multiple sequence alignment of the identified resistance genes was carried out using clustal-W (<http://www.genome.jp/tools/clustalw/>) and manually edited using Genedoc (<http://www.nrbcs.org/gfx/genedoc/>). The aligned sequences were subjected to the MEGA software for construction of phylogenetic tree using the NJ algorithm (Tamura *et al.*, 2013). The poisson correction robustness of clustering was checked by bootstrapping of 1000 replicates. Bootstrapping was used to evaluate the degree of support for a particular grouping pattern in the phylogenetic tree. The visualization of the phylogenetic tree was done by using fig tree. The evolutionary distances were computed using the Composite Likelihood method (Gao and Song, 2010) and expressed as number of base substitutions per site.

3.2.17 Motif prediction

The protein sequences of *Fusarium* resistance and defense genes were obtained using Multiple Expectation Maximization for Motif Elicitation suite 4.10.2 (<http://memesuite.org>) software and the Motif Alignment and Search Tool (MAST) (<http://meme.sdsc.edu/meme/website/intro.html>). To assess the functional motifs of annotated amino acid sequences, E-value was set 0.01 and motif length from 12 to 60.

3.2.18 Cis-regulatory element prediction

The *Fusarium* resistance genes and defense gene sequences and were searched against CRE's in the PlantCARE database (Lescot *et al.*, 2002).

3.2.19 Analysis of physico-chemical properties

ProtParam ExPASy (Gasteiger *et al.*, 2005) tool was used for calculating various physiochemical parameters (molecular weight, theoretical pI, GRAVY and instability index) of *Fusarium* resistance and defense related proteins. Protein sequences of *Fusarium* resistance, defense related genes were used as an input source. Molecular weight of protein is calculated by adding the average isotopic masses of amino acids (provided protein) and the average isotopic mass of one water molecule. Protein pI is

calculated using pKa values of amino acids. The GRAVY value for a protein was obtained by adding the hydropathy values of each amino acid residues and dividing by the number of residues in the length of the sequence. A protein whose instability index is smaller than 40 is predicted as stable and a value above 40 indicates that the protein are unstable.

3.2.20 Orthologs identification of defense genes and hormone signaling genes

We searched for orthologous proteins from closest species to mango (*i.e.* *Vitis vinifera* and *Populus trichocarpa*) whose PPI data were available and the orthologs of mango defense genes were retrieved from the BLAST analysis. Out of 10,760 orthologs of *Vitis vinifera*, 210 orthologs were selected with sequence identity $\geq 70\%$ or more with the 77 defense related genes obtained from transcriptomic data. In *Populous trichocarpa* orthologs, out of 11,839 orthologs, 303 orthologs were selected.

For the orthologs identification, phyto-hormone related genes (signaling pathways) were retrieved from the mango RNA-seq transcriptomic data of five different stages. We searched for orthologous proteins of hormone signaling genes from *Arabidopsis* Hormone Database (AHD2.0) whose PPI data were available (Jiang *et al.*, 2011). The orthologs of *Arabidopsis thaliana* phytohormone signaling pathway genes were retrieved through BLAST analysis. Among the signaling pathway genes, we observed 5,641 orthologs for 1081 signaling genes. Out of 5,641 orthologs, we observed that only 55 orthologs were having identity percent ≥ 70 which varied from 70 to 83.99. No orthologs were found for other hormones *i.e.* gibberellic acid, cytokinin, abscisic acid, ethylene, salicylic acid, jasmonic acid and brassinosteroids.

3.2.21 Network analysis of defense and hormone signaling genes

The gene Id list of the orthologs sequences of defense genes, hormone signaling genes were subjected to STRING (Jensen *et al.*, 2009) software for construction of gene network related to defense gene and hormone signaling genes. The results obtained from STRING were used for network analysis and visualization was done through cytoscape (Shannon *et al.*, 2003).

3.2.22 Identification of Transcription Factor

To find out the transcription factor in five samples, RNA-seq data was blasted with Plant transcription factor database (Jin *et al.*, 2014).

3.2.23 Identification of flowering genes

To identify the number and expression level flowering genes in mango transcriptome of five malformed and healthy buds at different growth stages, we blasted the unigenes sequences with *Arabidopsis thaliana* flowering gene database (Bouche *et al.*, 2016).

CHAPTER IV

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

**The man of science has learned to believe
in justification, not by faith, but by
verification**

-Thomas Henry Huxley

4.1.1 *De-novo* assembly, functional annotation, GO and COG analysis of transcripts and SSR mining in healthy and malformed tissues

4.1.1.1 *De-novo* assembly

The next generation sequencing resulted in 20,311,684, 20,773,211, 20,324,023, 27,924,723 and 18,598,750 PE reads for the five samples *i.e.* MB-1, MB-2, MB-3, HB-1 and HB-2 respectively (Table 1). Average transcripts length varied from a minimum of 1,014 bp in HB-2 to a maximum of 1121bp in MB-2. Maximum transcript length varied from 8,869bp in MB-1 to 1,1391bp in HB-2 whereas, Transcript N50 value was highest (1,768) in HB-1 and lowest (1,680) in HB-2. The unigenes size in both malformed tissues (MB-1:36,161; MB-2: 38,721 and MB-3:46,853) and healthy tissues (HB-1: 49,376 and HB-2: 52,741) showed increasing trends at different growth stages. Among the malformed stages, N50 for unigenes was minimum in MB-3 (1,624) and maximum in MB-2 (1677) whereas, in healthy tissues minimum was observed in HB-2 (1630) and maximum in HB-1(1723). The average GC content varied from 39.73 to 40.78 in malformed stages while in non-malformed (healthy) stages it varied very slightly *i.e.* 39.37 to 39.42%. The GC content percent in non-malformed stages was lesser compared to malformed buds at different growth stages. The GC content of five stages *i.e.* MB-1, MB-2, MB-3, HB-1 and HB-2 are 40.78%, 40.72%, 39.73%, 39.42% and 39.37% respectively (Table 1).

4.1.1.2 Functional Annotation

The assembled unigene sequences were used as query for the annotation of five different samples data using Blast-x searches based on non-redundant (NR) protein database of National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI).The summary of Blast-x annotation results are shown in the Table 2. Our results showed that with NR database out of 1, 52,807 unigenes sequences 147,832 (96.74%) were annotated through NR database, 79,895 (52.28%) were annotated through gene ontology and 44,982 (29.44%) were annotated through COG analysis

The alignment of unigene sequences of mango malformed and healthy samples with NR database showed matches with the different species (Fig.5a, b). *Citrus sinensis*,

Citrus clementina and *Theobroma cocoa* showed the highest number of unigene sequences matching among the five different samples which varied from 9,673 to 12,335, 7,096 to 9,023, and 2,078 to 2,736 respectively. Similarly, *Jatropha curcas* had 837-1064 number of unigenes matching with all five samples of mango followed by *Vitis vinifera* with 813 to 1064.

4.1.1.3 Gene ontology (GO)

Among the five different samples, the number of assigned GO terms varied from 13,749 (MB-1) to 17,733 (HB-1) in respect of total unigene sequences of their respective samples (Table 3). In single swollen malformed bud stage, total 70,009 GO assignments were obtained which were further classified into three gene ontology categories i.e. cellular component, biological process, and molecular function (Fig.6). Under the biological process, large numbers of unigenes (34,574) were categorized followed by cellular process (19,180) and molecular function category (16, 255). Under the biological process category, metabolic process (25.95%), cellular process (21.68%) and single-organism process (15.62%) were the top three most abundant subcategories. For the metabolic process, catalytic activity (44.18%) and binding (43.74%) represented the major proportion whereas, with respect to cellular process, cell (23.05%), cell part (22.52%), organelle (14.76%) and membrane (13.58%) were the dominant group (Fig.6).

In second stage *i.e.* multiple malformed bud stage, out of total 75,312 GO assignments (Table 3), under the biological process, large numbers of unigene sequences (36,919) were categorized, followed by cellular process (20,874) and molecular function (17,519). In biological process category, metabolic process (26.32%), cellular process (21.79%) and single-organism process (15.67%) represented the major proportion. The molecular function category had catalytic activity (44.23%) and binding (43.65%) whereas under cellular process, cell (22.84%), cell part (22.33%), organelle (14.62%) and membrane (13.82%) were the dominant abundant subcategories (Fig.6).

In malformed panicle development stage, out of 82,585 GO assignments under the biological process (Table 3), large numbers of unigenes sequence (40,958) were categorized followed by cellular process (22,499) and molecular function (19,128). In

biological process category, metabolic process (26.10%), cellular process (21.71%) and single-organism process (15.66%) represented the major proportion. The molecular function category had catalytic activity (44.05%) and binding (43.78%) whereas under cellular process, cell (22.91%), cell part (22.39%), organelle (14.75%) and membrane (13.85%) were the dominant abundant subcategories (Fig.6).

In healthy bud stage out of 87,877 GO assignment (Table 3), biological process category consist largest unigenes sequences (43,667) followed by cellular component (24,040) and molecular function (20,170). For the biological process category, metabolic process (25.92%), cellular process (21.66%) and single organism process (15.60%) represented the major proportion. In molecular function category, catalytic activity (44.00%) and binding (43.59%) whereas under the cellular process, cell (22.83%), cell part (22.32%) and organelle (14.72%) were the top most abundant subcategories (Fig. 7).

A total 89,451 GO assignment were obtained in healthy panicle development stage which were further classified into three gene ontology categories i.e. cellular component, biological process and molecular function (Table 3). Under the biological process, large numbers of unigenes (44,147) were categorized followed by cellular process (24,479) and molecular function category (20,825). Under the biological process category, metabolic process (26.50%), cellular process (21.79%) and single-organism process (15.72%) were the top three most abundant subcategories. For the metabolic process, catalytic activity (44.89%) and binding (42.76%) represented the major proportion whereas, with respect to cellular process, cell (22.76%), cell part (22.28%), organelle (14.73%) and membrane (13.78%) were the dominant group (Fig.7).

4.1.1.4 Clusters of orthologous groups (COG) analysis

We annotated the unigene sequences into the 26 COG categories to get effectiveness of our annotation process and completeness in our transcriptome data. The percent unigene sequences of COG category for MB-1, MB-2, MB-3, HB-1 and HB-2 are 20.25, 36.16, 35.44, 35.80 and 19.20 per cent respectively (Table 4).

In single swollen malformed bud stage, 5,275 of 26,044 (20.25%) sequences were assigned to the 26 COG categories (Table 4). The “general function prediction

only” category represented the largest group (960, 18.20%), followed by “function unknown” (708, 13.42%), “amino acid transport and metabolism” (418, 7.92%), “signal transduction mechanisms” (394, 7.47%), and “energy production and conversion” (393, 7.45%) whereas, the category which represent the lowest number of unigenes (< 1%) are “cell cycle control, cell division, chromosome partitioning” (38, 0.72%), “intracellular trafficking, secretion, and vesicular transport” (31, 0.59%) “cytoskeleton” (19, 0.36%) “cell motility” (12, 0.23%) “chromatin structure and dynamics” (11, 0.21%), “RNA processing and modification” (5, 0.09%) and “mobilome: prophages, transposons” (2, 0.04%) (Fig.8). In multiple malformed bud stage, 10,182 of 28,154 (36.17%) sequences were assigned to the COG classification (Table 4). The cluster *i.e.* “function unknown” consist of maximum (1800, 17.68%) unigenes sequences followed by “general function prediction only”, (1647, 16.18%), “signal transduction mechanisms” (874, 8.58%), “translation, ribosomal structure and biogenesis” (725, 7.12%), “amino acid transport and metabolism” (681, 6.69%), “posttranslational modification, protein turnover, chaperones” (667, 6.55%), “carbohydrate transport and metabolism” (559, 5.49%), and “energy production and conversion” (509, 5.00%) whereas, among the least number of unigenes category were “intracellular trafficking, secretion, and vesicular transport” (69, 0.68%), “cell cycle control, cell division, chromosome partitioning” (57, 0.56%), “cell motility” (53, 0.52%), “cytoskeleton” (23, 0.23%), “RNA processing and modification” (12, 0.12%), “mobilome: prophages, transposons” (12, 0.12%) and “chromatin structure and dynamics” (11, 0.11%)(Fig.8).

In malformed panicle development stage, 11,094 of 31,306 (35.44%) sequences were assigned to the COG classification (Table 4). The major COG categories of unigene sequences were “general function prediction only” (2110, 19.02%), “function unknown (1618, 14.58%), “translation, ribosomal structure and biogenesis” (853, 7.69%), “energy production and conversion” (720, 6.49%), “posttranslational modification, protein turnover, chaperones” (701, 6.32%), “signal transduction mechanisms” (697, 6.28%), “amino acid transport and metabolism” (646, 5.82%) and “carbohydrate transport and metabolism” (617, 5.56%) whereas, the category which represent the lowest number of unigenes (< 1%) are “cell cycle control, cell division, chromosome partitioning” (107, 0.96%), “intracellular trafficking, secretion, and

vesicular transport” (74,0.67%), “cell motility” (47,0.42%), “RNA processing and modification” (12,0.11%), “chromatin structure and dynamics” (12,0.11%), “mobilome: prophages, transposons” (8,0.07%) and “cytoskeleton” (3,0.03%) categories (Fig.8).

In healthy bud stage, 11,884 of 33,196 (35.80%) sequences were assigned to the 26 COG categories (Table 4). Among the COG categories higher number of unigene sequences were found in “general function prediction only” (2659,22.37%) followed by “function unknown” (2029,17.07%) “translation, ribosomal structure and biogenesis” (863,7.26%) “signal transduction mechanisms” (862,7.25%) “energy production and conversion” (694,5.84%), “posttranslational modification, protein turnover, chaperones” (688,5.79%) “carbohydrate transport and metabolism” (665,5.60%), “amino acid transport and metabolism” (657,5.53%) whereas lowest number were recorded in categories such as “intracellular trafficking, secretion, and vesicular transport” (77,0.65%), “cell motility” (52,0.44%) “cell cycle control, cell division, chromosome partitioning” (36,0.30%), “cytoskeleton” (32,0.27%), “chromatin structure and dynamics” (13,0.11%), “mobilome: prophages, transposons” (10,0.08%) and “RNA processing and modification” (7,0.06%) categories (Fig.9).

In healthy panicle development stage, 6,547 of 34,107 (19.20%) sequences were assigned to the COG classification (Table 4). The category *i.e.* “general function prediction only” contain the highest number (1050,16.04%) of unigene sequences followed by “function unknown” (786, 12.01%), “acid transport and metabolism” (551, 8.42%), “energy production and conversion” (507,7.74%), “carbohydrate transport and metabolism” (497,7.59%), “signal transduction mechanisms” (431,6.58%), “translation, ribosomal structure and biogenesis” (397,6.06%), “posttranslational modification, protein turnover, chaperones” (376,5.74%), whereas, least number of unigene sequences fall under “cell cycle control, cell division, chromosome partitioning” (48,0.73%) “intracellular trafficking, secretion, and vesicular transport” (37,0.57%), “cell motility” (26,0.40%), “cytoskeleton” (24,0.37%), “chromatin structure and dynamics” (14,0.21%), “RNA processing and modification” (12,0.18%) and “mobilome: prophages, transposons” (2,0.03%) categories (Fig.9).

In all the samples the maximum numbers of unigenes were observed in “general function prediction only” followed by “function unknown” except in multiple

malformed bud stages in which “function unknown” category contained highest number of unigenes sequences followed by “general function prediction only”. The other major unigenes categories are “translation, ribosomal structure and biogenesis”, “signal transduction mechanisms”, “energy production and conversion”, “posttranslational modification, protein turnover, chaperones”, “carbohydrate transport and metabolism”, “amino acid transport and metabolism” and “cell wall/membrane/envelope biogenesis” whereas, the category which represent the lowest number of unigenes in all five sample are “cell cycle control, cell division, chromosome partitioning”, “intracellular trafficking, secretion, and vesicular transport”, “cytoskeleton”, “cell motility”, “chromatin structure and dynamics”, “RNA processing and modification” and “mobilome: prophages, transposons”. The percentage of unigenes in defense COG categories was more in healthy tissues (Healthy bud stage, 2.95%; Healthy panicle development stage, 2.92%) as compared to unhealthy or malformed tissue (Single swollen malformed bud stage, 2.84%; Multiple malformed bud stage, 2.25% and Malformed panicle development stage, 2.23%).

4.1.1.5 Simple sequence repeats (SSRs) mining

SSRs are most commonly and extensively used molecular markers in plant breeding programs for determining genetic variations across species, due to high polymorphism rates, their high abundance, ease of development and broad distribution throughout the genome. Out of 1,52,807 sequences examined, total of 6,165 SSR markers were identified with maximum frequency of tri-nucleotide repeats (86.47%) followed by di-nucleotides (12.42%), tetra-nucleotide, hexa-nucleotide and penta-nucleotide (Fig.10). In the malformed samples, among the di-nucleotide repeats, AG/CT showed highest (9.46%) frequency followed by AT/AT (0.57%) and AC/GT (0.50%). In case of tri-nucleotide repeats, AAG/CTT showed highest occurrence (25.13%) followed by ATC/ATG (14.07%), ACC/GGT (10.42%), AGG/CCT (7.18%), AGC/CTG (6.75%), AAC/GTT (5.96%), AAT/ATT (2.83%), CCG/CGG (2.16%) and ACT/AGT (1.10%) with the least (0.96%) in ACG/CGT (Fig.11a). In the healthy samples, among the di-nucleotide repeats, AG/CT showed highest (9.67%) frequency followed by AC/GT (0.82%) and AT/AT (0.82%). In case of tri-nucleotide repeats, AAG/CTT showed highest occurrence (25.42%) followed by ACC/GGT (9.01%), AGC/CTG (7.12%),

AGG/CCT (6.92%), AAC/GTT (5.09%), AAT/ATT (2.94%), CCG/CGG (1.90%) and ACG/CGT (1.01%) along with the least (0.72%) being in ACT/AGT (Fig.11b).

4.1.2 Total differentially expressed transcripts in malformed and healthy tissues

Differential gene expression analysis was performed to study the expression level variations in healthy and malformed tissues of mango variety Amrapali at different growth stages. To identify malformed specific DEGs a six-way venn diagram was prepared from the whole gene expression profile for up-regulated and down-regulated genes (Fig. 12 and 13). Among the six possible combinations (Table 5), out of 84,651 transcript's, 5814 (6.87%) were significantly expressed at ≥ 2 -fold change (P, 0.05). The significantly expressed genes in different stages *i.e.* HB-1 vs MB-1, HB-2 vs MB-2; HB-1 vs MB-2, HB-1 vs MB-3 and HB-2 vs MB-1 and HB-2 vs MB-3 are 818, 912, 1057, 941, 1007 and 1079 respectively (Table 5). The venn analysis of up-regulated genes indicate that there are 147, 162, 230, 369, 568 and 404 unique DEG's in cluster A, B, C, D, E and F respectively. Heatmap representing the top 100 significantly expressed genes between HB-1 vs MB-1, HB-2 vs MB-2; HB-1 vs MB-2, HB-1 vs MB-3 and HB-2 vs MB-1 and HB-2 vs MB-3 are shown in Fig.14 and 15).

4.1.3 Differentially expressed transcripts for plant hormones

To understand the interaction effect of different plant hormone genes with malformation we observed the differentially expressed transcripts in HB-1 vs MB-1, HB-2 vs MB-2 and HB-2 vs MB-3. The differential expression analysis at HB-1 vs MB-1 stage, indicated that the number of up-regulated transcript for auxin, gibberellin, ABA and ethylene are 2, 3, 1 and 3 respectively, whereas one each transcript of auxin and ethylene hormone were down-regulated. The maximum \log_2 fold change was observed for CDS_18598_Unigene_19531 (6.83) followed by CDS_30966_Unigene_40602 (6.29) and CDS_27786_Unigene_31862 (4.53). The down-regulated transcript of ethylene and auxin are CDS_6551_Unigene_7106 (-3.10), and CDS_872_Unigene_1048 (-2.88) respectively (Table 6). At HB-2 vs MB-2 stage (Table 7), eight transcript of phytohormone (auxin: 2; GA: 2; cytokinin: 1 and ethylene: 3) were up-regulated and five transcripts were down-regulated (auxin: 2; GA: 1 and ethylene: 2). Highest \log_2 fold change was observed for gibberellic acid transcript *i.e.* CDS_2893_Unigene_3247 (4.03) followed by ethylene transcript *i.e.*

CDS_2728_Unigene_3080 (3.76) and cytokinin related transcript *i.e.* CDS_19956_Unigene_20863 (3.68).

During panicle development stage (HB-2 vs MB-3), five transcripts were up-regulated and three transcripts were down-regulated. Highest log₂ fold change was observed for CDS_25415_Unigene_27785 (3.8) followed by CDS_6639_Unigene_7056 (3.1), CDS_20980_Unigene_22019 (2.8) and CDS_24125_Unigene_25942 (2.6). Among the down-regulated transcripts, only three transcripts of auxin were down-regulated *i.e.* CDS_7970_Unigene_8341 (-4.23), CDS_13708_Unigene_14197 (-3.67) and CDS_9784_Unigene_10223 (Table 7).

4.1.4. Differential expression of flowering genes

Floral malformation is flowering oriented phenomenon in mango hence we observed the differential expression of flowering genes to find out their correlation with malformation. The differential of expression flowering related transcripts showed that at bud stage (HB-1 vs MB-1 stage) 17 transcripts were up-regulated and six transcripts were down-regulated (Table 8). The transcripts having highest log₂ fold change was observed in LDL2 (CDS_18357_Unigene_21030: 7.0) followed by TPL (CDS_2996_Unigene_3428: 4.6), NUC (CDS_7452_Unigene_8210: 4.0), TIC (CDS_2531_Unigene_2931: 3.7), AGL8 (CDS_21476_Unigene_25810: 3.5), WRKY34 (CDS_4156_Unigene_4674: 3.5), WRKY 34 (CDS_641_Unigene_800: 3.4), MYB-30 (CDS_30130_Unigene_37919:3.4) and REF6 (CDS_14330_Unigene_15945: 3.2). The six down-regulated transcripts related to flowering were RRM/RBD/ RNP motifs (CDS_10516_Unigene_11473: -4.1), SDG25 (CDS_15588_Unigene_17495: -3.6), SPL5 (CDS_20744_Unigene_24555: -3.6), CLF (CDS_15649_Unigene_17557: -4.2), TIL1 (CDS_25467_Unigene_34490: -5.1) and TIC (CDS_12022_Unigene_12654: -3.1).

Differentially expressed flowering genes in healthy panicle development stage (HB-2) compared to multiple malformed bud (MB-2) stages revealed that 17 transcripts were up-regulated and 14 were down-regulated (Table 9). The highly up-regulated flowering related transcripts was UBP12 followed by AGL24, KIN10, MYB30, GID1B and RFI2. The highly down-regulated transcripts were AGL6 (CDS_823_Unigene_979:-7.6), GCT (CDS_15389_Unigene_15939: -6.0), AGL8

(CDS_459_Unigene_555: -5.7), DCL3 (CDS_22931_Unigene_24379: -5.1), MYB30 (CDS_733_Unigene_882: -5.1) and AGL6 (CDS_2107_Unigene_2407: -5.0). The other down-regulated transcripts observed were SUVR5, GA₃OX1, GA₂₀OX3, PIF4, UBP12 and SPL9 (Table 9).

During panicle development stage (HB-2 vs MB-3), 13 flowering related transcripts were up-regulated and 21 transcripts were down-regulated (Table 10). The highly up-regulated transcript were of UBP12 (CDS_30212_Unigene_38048:6.5), EFS (CDS_32261_Unigene_45008), and RFI2 (CDS_5926_Unigene_6339:5.6); whereas down-regulated transcripts were TIC (CDS_1441_Unigene_1667: -6.0), GA₃OX1 (CDS_8241_Unigene_8633: -5.6), TPS1 (CDS_23881_Unigene_25609: -4.7), and TPL (CDS_34031_Unigene_52536: -4.5). Three transcripts of MYB30 and two transcripts of TPL were down-regulated at HB-2 vs MB-3 stage (Table 10).

4.1.5 Differential expression of transcription factors

The differentially expressed transcription factor at HB-1 vs MB-1 stage revealed that 21 transcripts were up-regulated and 6 were down-regulated. Among them the most up-regulated transcription factor observed were WRKY followed by ERF. The WRKY TF-31 (5.72) and CBF/DREB TF-1 (5.60) were highly up-regulated whereas TTF GT-3b (-7.33) was highly down-regulated (Table 11).

In healthy panicle development stage compared to multiple malformed bud, total 20 transcription factors were up-regulated while 10 were down-regulated. The number of up-regulated transcription factors were MYB (5) followed by WRKY (3) and ERF (2), whereas bHLH (3) and AP2 (2) were among the mostly down-regulated transcription factors. The highest up-regulated transcription factor was WRKY TF 75 (7.35), WRKY TF 47 (5.67), K-box and MADS box (5.60) whereas highly down-regulated transcription factor were Kow TF1 (-5.56), WER (-4.82) and E2FC (-4.32) (Table 12). The number of differentially expressed transcription factors at panicle development stage *i.e.* HB-2 vs MB-3 (Table 13) showed eight up-regulated and six down regulated transcription factors. The highly up-regulated transcription factor was WRKY TF 75 (6.01), HBP-1a (4.04) and WRKY TF 70 (3.51) whereas PIF7 (-3.71) was highly down-regulated followed by bHLH67 (-2.63).

4.1.6 Differential expression of protein kinase gene

Analysis of differential expression of protein kinase related transcript at bud stage (HB vs MB-1) revealed 22 up-regulated and 10 down-regulated transcripts related to protein kinase. The highly up-regulated and down-regulated protein related transcripts were LRR-RLK RPK2-1 (5.62) and LRR-RLK (-6.79) respectively. High number of protein kinase related transcripts were up-regulated for leucine rich repeat-receptor like kinases (6) followed by serine/threonine protein kinase (4), receptor like kinase (3) and GsSRK (2) whereas among the down-regulated transcripts, four transcript of leucine rich repeat-receptor like kinases followed by two transcripts of serine/threonine protein kinase were observed (Table 14). We observed that at HB-2 vs MB-2 stage, 13 transcripts were up-regulated whereas no transcripts were down-regulated. The highly up-regulated transcript were CDS_9905_Unigene_10339 (5.16) followed by CDS_31913_Unigene_43877 (4.63) and CDS_15934_Unigene_16539 (4.22). Two transcripts of each protein kinase *i.e.* RLK, GsSRK, CBL-IPK2, ser/thre PK were up-regulated during this stage (Table 15).

The differential expression analysis of protein kinase at panicle development stage (HB-2 vs MB-3) revealed that 10 transcripts were upregulated and eight transcripts were downregulated. The highly upregulated transcript was for cysteine-rich RLK 10 *i.e.* CDS_32631_Unigene_46474 (5.26) followed by CDS_31913_Unigene_43877 (4.75) and LRR-RLK (3.87). Two each transcripts were up regulated for LRR-RLK, ser/thre PK, CBL-IPK and RLK. The highly down-regulated transcripts were observed for CDS_12985_Unigene_13425 (-5.97) followed by CDS_10904_Unigene_11357 (-3.94). Mostly serine/threonine protein kinase related transcripts were down-regulated during the panicle development stages (Table 15).

4.1.7 Differential expression of resistance proteins/genes

In our study, out of 16 differentially expressed transcripts related to resistance proteins/genes in mango transcriptome, six transcripts were up-regulated and 10 transcripts were down regulated (Table 16). Among R-genes/proteins, TMV, RPM-1, RGA-3, pleotropic drug disease resistance and NB-ARC domain containing disease resistance protein were significantly expressed. The number of up-regulated transcripts

between HB-1 vs MB-1, HB-2 vs MB-2 and HB-2 vs MB-3 stages were 1, 2, and 3 whereas down-regulated transcripts were 4, 1, and 5 respectively (Table 16). The transcripts related to NB-ARC domain-containing and TMV resistance protein were commonly down-regulated at bud stage (HB-1 vs MB-1), and panicle development stages (HB-2 vs MB-3).

4.2 Functional annotations, pathway and gene networks of the differentially expressed genes (DEGs)

4.2.1 Functional annotation of transcripts in healthy and malformed tissues.

The differentially expressed genes in GO (gene ontology) categories of five different samples (Table 17) varied from 783 (MB-2) to 1100 (HPS-2). The total differentially expressed genes in healthy buds (HB-1:938 and HB-2: 1100) were more compared to malformed buds *i.e.* MB-1 (834), MB-2 (783) and MB-3 (997). In both healthy and malformed buds at different development stages, significantly differentially expressed genes were found under molecular functional categories followed by biological process and cellular process. In single swollen malformed bud stage, out of 834 differentially expressed GO assignments, molecular function categories had most number of unigenes (716) followed by biological process (667) and cellular component (350). Under the biological process, large numbers of unigenes (34,574) were categorized followed by cellular process (19,180) and molecular function category (16,255). In multiple malformed bud stage, a total 783 DEG's were categorized into biological process (626), cellular process (324) and molecular function (676). In malformed panicle development stage, a total of 997 DEG's were categorized into molecular functional categories followed by biological process and cellular process having 861, 797 and 420 unigenes respectively. In healthy bud stage out of 938 differentially expressed GO assignment, most number of transcripts (799) fell under molecular functional categories followed by biological process (755) and cellular process (387) whereas in healthy panicle development stage had most number of differentially expressed genes *i.e.* 1100 which were classified into in molecular functional categories followed by biological process and cellular process with a number of 948, 896 and 470 DEG's respectively (Table 17). The differentially expressed

transcript of top ten categories in biological process, molecular function, and cellular process of malformed and healthy stages are described in Fig. 16 and 17 respectively.

4.2.2 Pathway analysis of transcripts in healthy and malformed tissues.

Among the 207 KEGG pathways, highest number of uni-transcripts fell under metabolism, followed by genetic information processing, environmental information processing, cellular processes and organismal system (Fig.18). In the metabolic pathways, the transcripts were mostly found in carbohydrate which varied from 468 (SSMBS-1) to 563 (HBS-1), followed by amino acid, carbon, energy, lipid metabolism and least were observed in xenobiotics biodegradation and metabolism (63 in MB-1). In various pathways of all five samples, it was observed that there were less number of genes involved in malformed tissues compared to healthy tissues except in biosynthesis of other secondary metabolites (metabolism), signaling molecules and interaction (environmental information processing) and environmental adaptation (Fig 18).

Apart from the above KEGG pathways analysis, we also observed the differential expression of transcripts in all 207 KEGG pathways (Table 18). In metabolic pathway, differentially expressed genes were more prominent in carbohydrate metabolism followed by amino acid metabolism, carbon metabolism, lipid metabolism and biosynthesis of other secondary metabolite pathways. In the genetic information processing pathways, “translation” and “folding, sorting and degradation”, in environmental information processing pathway “signal transduction pathway” and in cellular process, “cell growth and death” pathways were having more number of differentially expressed transcripts. Among all studied KEGG pathways, signal transduction pathways are having highest number of differentially expressed transcripts. The number of differential expressed transcripts were increasing from bud to panicle development stages whereas in healthy stages, decreasing trend was observed from bud to panicle development (Table 18).

Carbohydrate metabolism pathway

The KEGG pathway analysis of carbon metabolism pathway revealed that most transcripts were observed for “starch and sucrose metabolism”, “glycolysis/gluconeogenesis”, “amino sugar & nucleotide sugar metabolism”, “pyruvate metabolism”, and “glyoxylate and dicarboxylate metabolism” (Fig. 19). The differential

expression analysis of transcripts related to carbon metabolism pathway indicated that at bud stage, high numbers of differential expressed transcripts were observed in healthy bud (HB-1) stage compared to single swollen malformed bud (MB-1) except “fructose and mannose metabolism” and “galactose metabolism” (Table 19). The number of differential expressed transcript related to pathways *i.e.* “amino sugar and nucleotide sugar metabolism”, “glyoxylate and dicarboxylate metabolism” “glycolysis/gluconeogenesis”, and “ascorbate and aldarate metabolism” were more in healthy buds (HB-1 & HB-2) compared to malformed buds (MB-1 & MB-3).

Amino acid metabolism pathway

The analysis of transcripts in 13 pathways related to amino acid metabolism revealed that most transcript were observed in “arginine and proline metabolism”, “cysteine and methionine metabolism”, “glycine, serine and threonine metabolism”, “phenylalanine metabolism”, “phenylalanine, tyrosine and tryptophan biosynthesis” (Table 20). To get the clear cut idea regarding the expression of transcripts in 13 amino acid related pathways, we conducted the differential expression analysis (Fig.20). We observed that differential expressed transcripts related to amino acid metabolism pathways were more in healthy buds (HB-1 & HB-2) compared to malformed buds (MB-1 & MB-3) except “valine, leucine and isoleucine degradation, “valine, leucine and isoleucine biosynthesis”, “histidine metabolism”, and “tryptophan metabolism”.

Energy metabolism pathway

We analyzed that transcript related to energy pathways were mainly observed for eight pathways. The maximum number of transcripts were observed in “oxidative phosphorylation”, “photosynthesis”, “carbon fixation in photosynthetic organisms”, and “methane metabolism”. At both bud and panicle development stages (Table 21), the number of transcripts related to “oxidative phosphorylation” and “methane metabolism” pathways were higher in healthy buds (HB-1 vs MB-1) compared to malformed stages (HB-2 and MB-3). The number of differentially expressed transcript were higher in healthy stages (HB-1 and HB-2) compared to malformed stages (MB-1 and MB-3) for “oxidative phosphorylation” pathway (Fig. 21).

Lipid metabolism pathway

The high number transcript related to lipid metabolism pathway were observed in “glycero phospholipid metabolism” followed by “glycerolipid metabolism”, “fatty acid degradation” and “fatty acid biosynthesis” (Table 22). At bud stage, the differentially expressed transcripts related to lipid metabolism pathway were more in healthy bud stage (HB-1) compared to single swollen malformed bud stage (MB-1) whereas at panicle development stage similar number of differential expressed transcripts were observed in healthy (HB-2) and malformed panicle development stages (MB-3) except “glycerolipid metabolism” pathway which had higher number in MB-3 compare to HB-2 (Fig. 22).

Biosynthesis of secondary metabolite pathways

In nature, plant and fungi produces a plethora of secondary metabolites that regulates not only the growth and development process but also modulate the plant defense process through which they are able to resist several kinds of biotic and abiotic stresses. Because of their prominent role in plant defense we studied several biosynthesis pathways which produce secondary metabolites. The transcriptome of healthy and malformed tissues revealed 16 pathways related to biosynthesis of secondary metabolites and number of transcripts present in 16 pathways are described in the table 23 . At bud stages, most of the transcripts related to “phenylpropanoid biosynthesis”, “flavonoid biosynthesis”, “tropane, piperidine and pyridine alkaloid biosynthesis”, “isoquinoline alkaloid biosynthesis”, “stilbenoid, diarylheptanoid and gingerol biosynthesis”, “streptomycin biosynthesis”, “monobactam biosynthesis” and “butirosin and neomycin biosynthesis” were higher in healthy bud stages (HB-1) compared to single swollen malformed stages (MB-1) whereas transcripts related to “anthocyanin biosynthesis”, “isoflavonoid biosynthesis”, “betalain biosynthesis” and “novobiocin biosynthesis” were slightly more in single swollen malformed stages (MB-1) compared to healthy bud stages (HB-1). Among all the pathways studied phenylpropanoid biosynthesis related transcripts are relatively higher in healthy bud stage (HB-1: 73) compared to single swollen malformed bud stage (MB-1:68) whereas at panicle development stage, transcripts were higher in malformed panicle development stage (MB-3: 78) compared to healthy panicle development stage (HB-2).

For having better understanding of the expression of transcripts in above pathways we performed the differential expression analysis of transcripts in above pathways (Fig.23). Among 16 pathways related to biosynthesis of secondary metabolites, differentially expressed transcripts were observed in ten pathways while six pathways didn't show the differentially expressed transcripts. We found that differentially expressed transcripts related to “phenylpropanoid biosynthesis” and “flavonoid biosynthesis” were more in healthy bud (HB-1) compared to single swollen malformed bud stage (MB-1).

Plant pathogen interaction pathways

The interaction among plant and pathogen are complex in nature and difficult to understand and this interaction involves several genes that regulate the plant defense. So to overcome this complexity, transcripts profiling serve as a powerful techniques for examining the expression of the several genes that are transcriptionally regulated in plant pathogen interaction pathway. Therefore we performed the transcript profiling of healthy and malformed tissues for plant pathogen interaction pathways. In our study we observed transcript profiling of 28 genes that are involved in plant pathogen interaction pathways and their copy number in MB-1, MB-2, MB-3, HB-1 and HB-2 stages are 107, 118, 113, 116 and 96 respectively (Table 24). We observed that most transcripts were related to calcium binding protein CML followed by calcium dependent protein kinase (CDPK), calmodulin (CALM). To get clear cut idea about the role of gene involved in plant pathogen interaction pathways we observed the differential expression of all those genes (Fig. 24). We found that, among 28 genes category, genes of 13 categories were differentially expressed and their total number were higher in both healthy bud (HB-1: 11) and healthy panicle developmental stages (HB-2: 8) compare to single swollen malformed bud (MB-1: 05) and malformed panicle development stage (MB-3: 06). At bud and panicle development stages, the number differentially expressed transcripts of calcium binding protein CML were higher in healthy buds compared to malformed buds.

Signaling transduction pathways

The analysis of KEGG pathways revealed that most of the transcripts in category of environmental information processing were of signal transduction. We observed that

transcript of healthy and malformed buds belonged to 28 signaling pathways. Among all 28 signaling pathways, transcripts were related to “plant hormone signal transduction pathway” followed by “PI3K-Akt signaling pathway”, “AMPK signaling pathway”, “FoxO signaling pathway”, “Wnt signaling pathway” and “cAMP signaling pathway” were higher in healthy bud and panicle development stages compared to malformed bud and panicle development stages (Table 25). The differential expression of transcripts present in all 28 signaling pathways (Fig.25) showed that transcripts related to “plant hormone signal transduction”, “Ras signaling pathway” and “hedgehog signaling pathway” were more in healthy buds (HB-1 and HB-2) compared to malformed buds (MB-1 and MB-3). In malformed buds (MB-1 and MB-3) differential expressed transcripts of “AMPK signaling pathway”, “MAPK signaling pathway”, and “VEGF signaling pathway” were more compared to healthy bud (HB-1) and panicle development stages (HB-2).

Phytohormone signaling pathway related transcripts

Plant hormone biosynthesis and signaling pathway related transcripts are enlisted in table 26 and 27 whereas differentially expressed transcripts of hormone signaling are described in Fig.26. High number of jasmonic acid biosynthesis pathway related transcripts were observed followed by salicylic acid, cytokinin, auxin, ethylene, GA and brassinosteroids. Auxin biosynthesis genes i.e. YUCCA/YUC were higher in healthy buds compared to malformed buds whereas S-AMS (ethylene), beta oxidase (jasmonic acid) related transcripts were higher in healthy buds (HB-1) compared to single swollen malformed bud (MB-1). We observed that CKx, UGT (Cytokinin), PAL (salicylic acid), lipoxygenase (jasmonic acid) related transcripts were higher in malformed buds (MB-1 & MB-2) compared to healthy buds (HB-1 & HB-2).

The analysis of phytohormone signaling related transcripts revealed that maximum number of transcripts was observed for auxin signaling genes followed by abscisic acid, cytokinin, ethylene, salicylic acid, brassinosteroids and gibberellic acid. The transcripts of AUX-IAA (auxin), ABF (abscisic acid), BSK (brassinosteroid) were higher in healthy buds (HB-1 & HB-2) compared to malformed buds (MB-1 & MB-3). The total numbers of phytohormone signaling related transcripts at HB-1 stage were higher than the MB-1 stages indicating that signaling pathway is more active in HB-1

stage. The differential expressed transcript of hormone signaling revealed that signaling gene i.e. SAUR (auxin) and ABF (abscisic acid) were higher in both healthy buds (HB-1 & HB-2) compared to malformed buds (MB-1 & MB-2). The PP2C (abscisic acid) and ETR (ethylene) related transcripts were highly expressed at single swollen malformed bud stage compared to healthy bud stage.

4.2.3 Network analysis of differentially expressed defense related transcripts, phytohormone signaling pathways in healthy and malformed tissues

4.2.3.1 Network analysis of defense genes

We found 185 unigenes in healthy bud stage and 170 unigenes from healthy panicle stage which were related to different defense categories *i.e.* R-genes, mitogen activated protein kinase, transcription factor, enzyme and multiple drug resistant gene. Mango transcriptomic data resulted a total of 77 defense related genes with a log fold change ≥ 2 . Out of 77 defense related genes, 49 genes were from healthy bud stages (Annexes table 4) and 28 from healthy panicle stages (Annexes table 5). The expression of 77 selected genes from healthy stages (healthy bud stage and healthy panicle stage) were compared with three malformed stages *i.e.* single swollen malformed bud stage (MB-1), multiple malformed bud stage (MB-2) and malformed panicle stage (MB-3). The expression of these defense genes are depicted through heat map (Fig.27).

4.2.3.1.1 Network analysis of defense genes between *Mangifera indica* and *Vitis vinifera*

The orthologs of *Vitis vinifera* were retrieved and subjected to STRING software to find protein-protein interactions. Further the network analysis and visualization was done through cytoscape software. After PPI network analysis, these orthologs of *Vitis vinifera* were replaced with the mango defense related orthologs. The PPI network of mango defense gene was depicted in Fig. 28 and minimum confidence score was kept high (0.700). In the network we observed that 38 proteins were more actively interacted. The number of nodes and edges in PPI network with *Vitis vinifera* were 104 and 151. The average node degree was 2.9 while clustering coefficient was 0.721. The expected number of edges were 12 while PPI enrichment p-value was zero. Among 38 nodes, maximum nodes (28) were from heat shock protein followed by SHMT (4), CCR (2), SOD (2), MAPK (2), WRKY-33 (1) and HY5 (1).

4.2.3.1.2 Network analysis of defense genes between *Mangifera indica* and *Populus trichocarpa*

The id of protein orthologs of *Populus trichocarpa* were retrieved and subjected to STRING software for interaction in between the proteins of *Populus trichocarpa*. After interaction gene network was built from the orthologs. Further the network analysis and visualization through was done through cytoscape software. After gene network analysis, these orthologs id of *Populus trichocarpa* were replace with the mango defense gene id. The gene network of mango defense gene was depicted in Fig. 29. For minimum required interaction the confidence score was kept high (0.700) and in display setting mode, disconnected node in the network was selected. In gene network we observed that 45 nodes are more actively interacting. The number of nodes and edges in gene network with *Vitis vinifera* were 125 and 286. The average node degree was 4.58 while clustering coefficient was 0.688. The expected number of edges was 25 while PPI enrichment p-value was zero. Among 45 nodes, maximum nodes (35) were from heat shock protein followed by SHMT (3), SOD (2), WRKY 33 (2), MAPK (1), CCR (1) and LHY5 (1).

4.2.3.2 Network analysis of phyto-hormone signaling genes

The gene network of mango phytohormone signaling pathway genes are depicted in Fig. 30 in which minimum required interaction score was kept high (0.700). In gene network, among all the phytohormone genes, we found that only auxin signaling gene proteins were more actively interacted whereas in our study no interaction were observed for other hormones like gibberellic acid, cytokinin, abscisic acid, ethylene, salicylic acid, jasmonic acid and brassinosteroids. We observed one types of interaction network for auxin signaling genes. The auxin interacting genes in the gene network are AUX-IAA, and ARF. The signaling genes in the gene network interaction network includes 12 nodes and 24 edges. The average node degree was 4 while clustering coefficient was 0.561. The expected number of edges were zero while PPI enrichment p-value was zero indicating that proteins have more interactions among themselves than what would be expected for a random set of proteins of similar size, drawn from the genome.

4.3 Identification of homologous gene sequence between mango and *Fusarium* species from the transcriptome of healthy and malformed tissue and *in-silico* analysis of *Fusarium* resistance genes

4.3.1 Identification of homologous gene sequences between mango and *Fusarium* species

A higher number of genes (MB-1:219; MB-2:164 and MB-3:236) having similarity with different *Fusarium* species were expressed in malformed tissues in comparison with the healthy tissues (HB-1:99 and HB-2:129). Among the *Fusarium* species, maximum number of transcripts were related to *F. fujikurui* followed by *F. subglutinans* and *F. proliferatum*. The whole genome transcriptomic data for *F. mangiferae* is not available in public domain. Hence out of 122 EST sequence of *F. mangiferae*, only one unigenes from transcriptome data of mango matched with *F. mangiferae* in malformed tissues at single swollen malformed bud stage (MB-1) and malformed panicle stage where no transcripts were observed in healthy tissues. The number of *Fusarium* related transcripts were higher (1.5 to 2 times more) in number compare to healthy stages (Table 28).

4.3.2. *In-silico* analysis of *Fusarium* resistance genes of different plant species

4.3.2.1. Multiple sequence alignment and phylogenetic analysis

Nucleotide sequences of *Fusarium* resistance genes were used to find out the homologous sequences which served as a benchmark for developing resistant genes for unknown *Fusarium* related diseases in annual, biennial and perennial horticultural crops. The results of multiple sequence alignment are depicted in Fig 31. The constructed phylogenetic tree was divided into three main groups, namely A, B, and C (Fig 32). The group A consist of one gene (I2 clone 2956), whereas group B had six genes (I2 clone 3333, I2 clone 2958, I2 clone 2950, I2 clone 3324, I2 clone 3336 and I2 clone 2942) belonging to dicot species, *Solanum lycopersicum*. The group C had highest (58 gene) *Fusarium* resistance genes which were further classified into three different subgroups *i.e.* C1, C2, and C3 on the basis of their protein motifs. The subgroup-C1 comprises of 19 genes (tomato species) with four conserved motifs (motif-1, 2, 3 and 4) and subgroup-C2, a very complicated subgroup, comprising of 25 genes of 9 different

plant species (*arabidopsis*, banana, *lilium*, melon, onion, rice, soya bean, tobacco and tomato) and one from yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) and one from fungi (*Trichoderma harzianum*) with no conserved motif, whereas subgroup-C3 consisted of 13 genes belonging to banana with three conserved motifs (motif 1, 3 and 5). The *Fusarium* resistance genes presented in group A, showed more similar conserved motif pattern with group B followed by subgroup C1 and C3 (Fig. 32).Subgroup C2 was unique as compared to other groups and subgroups.

4.3.2.2. Motif prediction

In-silico motif analysis of 65 *Fusarium* resistance genes for motif prediction, using MEME program, revealed 46 sequences having a p-value less than 0.0001 and E-value less than 10. Overall five significant motifs with minimum and maximum width of 12 and 60 respectively were mined for resistance genes, and are designated as motifs 1, motif 2, motif 3, motif 4 and motif 5 (Table 29). Among all the genes studied, motif-3 was present in 43 genes followed by motif-1 in 40 genes, motif-2 in 28 genes, motif-4 in 26 genes and motif-5 was present in 13 genes (Fig.33). The gene NBS-15, chit-42, Lr14-3-3 and beta-glucanase had one motif, NBS-16 gene had two motifs, whereas 16 genes had three motifs and 24 genes had four motifs (Fig. 33). The maximum E-value was (9.9e-129) in NBS-5 gene, while minimum (0.00065) was observed in NBS-15 gene.

4.3.2.3 *Cis*-regulatory elements

Analysis of 65 resistance genes resulted in 92 types of *cis*-regulatory elements. Among them CAAT-box had maximum (65) frequency (present in all the resistance genes) followed by G-box (54), Skn-1_motif (44), ARE (42), TC-rich repeats (36), CGTCA-motif (36), TGACG-motif (36), circadian (35), Sp1(35), O2-site (34), A-box (33), Box I (33), AAGAA-motif (32), MBS (32), TATA-box (32) and TATCCAT/C-motif (32). The functions of different *cis*-regulatory elements are described in Table 30. According to differences in function, *cis*-regulatory elements were divided into 11 categories along with unknown function category.

4.3.2.4 Physico-chemical properties of *Fusarium* resistance genes

Protein domain analysis indicated that among the 65 gene sequences, molecular weight of the proteins ranged from a minimum of 5710.40 (I-2 clone Heamsona) to a maximum of 144827.10 (I-2 complete cds) (Annexes Table 3). The pI of protein value ranged from 4.17 to 11.12. Among the 65 protein sequences, 78.46 per cent showed slightly acidic character whereas remaining 21.54 per cent were in basic character with a pI of ≥ 8 . The instability index of the protein sequences observed was minimum in CHS-7 and maximum with 88.31 in I-2-clone Heamsona (Annexes Table 3). Out of 65 sequences, 32 protein sequences were instable, whereas 33 protein sequences were stable in nature. The grand average of hydropathicity (GRAVY) in the 65 *Fusarium* resistance gene sequences ranged from -0.507 (NBS-16) to 0.898 (CHS-7).

4.3.2.5. Binding sites and hydrophobicity analysis of protein sequence

Protein binding sites and level of hydrophobicity in the five stable genes *i.e.* beta-glucanase, I-2-clone-2942, I-7, chit-42 and NBS-15 were represented in the Fig 34. The binding sites in proteins were represented by green portion whereas the hydrophobicity was represented by brown color and blue color represents hydrophilic nature of proteins. The distribution pattern in five genes for binding site is more, while hydrophobicity is very low to low.

4.3.2.6. Conserved domain search and trans-membrane prediction

The conserved domain analysis revealed one type of conserved domain in each of five stable *Fusarium* resistance genes except Chit-42 and I-7 which had two domains almost similar in function. Among the genes studied for CD-search, β -glucanase, I-2-2942 and NBS-15 had Glyco-hydro-1 superfamily, P-loop NTPase superfamily and NB-ARC domain respectively. The two conserved domains in Chit-42 gene were GH-18 chitinase-like and Glyco-18 whereas LRR-RI domain was conserved in I-7 gene. According to THHM Model, trans-membrane helix was present in extending residues from 907 to 929 of I-7 gene, while it was absent in rest of four genes (β -glucanase, chit-42, I-2-2942 and NBS-15).

4.3.2.7 Secondary and tertiary structural analysis of protein sequences

Secondary structure analysis was done for five genes which were most stable in nature on the basis of instability index belonging to three plants (tomato, banana and soybean) and one fungal species (*Trichoderma harzianum*). The secondary structure composed of alpha helix, beta strand, disordered and TM helix. The secondary structure results of five stable proteins indicated that alpha helix percentage was highest (52%) in NBS-15 gene (banana) while minimum was observed in I-7 (20%). The beta strand varied from 10% (I-2 and I-7) to 24% in beta-glucanase whereas disordered percentage varied from 15 to 27% (Table 31).

The 3D structure (Fig 34) predicted the arrangement of secondary structures as well as their side chains into three-dimensional space. The results of Ramachandran plot analysis were divided into three main categories *i.e.* favoured region, allowed region and outlier region (Fig 35). The favoured region (97.4%) was maximum in Chit-42, followed by β -glucanase (94.2%), NBS-15 (85.2%), I2-Clone-2942 (84.7%) and I-7 (76.7%); whereas allowed region was highest in I-7 (15.2%), followed by NBS-15 (9.7%), I-2 (8.9%), β -glucanase (5.8%) and Chit-42 (2.1%) (Table 35). The Z score predicted by ProSA-web tool in I-2, I-7, NBS-15, chit-42 and β -glucanase were -7.35, -7.66, -4.68, -3.30 and -2.95 respectively (Table 33) and were obtained by X-ray crystallography (light blue) as well as NMR spectroscopy (dark blue) in five stable protein sequences of *Fusarium* resistance genes (Fig.36). Whereas according to Verify-3D, in beta-glucanase, 95.08% residues had 3D-1D profile ≥ 0.2 followed by 89.60% residues in chit-42 and 76.09% in I-7 (Table 33).

CHAPTER V

DISCUSSION

The opposite of the correct sentence is false statement but the opposite of a profound truth may well another profound truth

-Niels Bohr

Transcriptomic approach includes the study of expression of coding, non-coding and small RNA's both quantitatively and qualitatively in high throughput manner. Besides identifying the gene expression it also helps in understanding gene's transcriptional status, PTM (post transcriptional modifications), alternate splicing patterns, 5'end and 3'end sites of genome. In present era it is most widely used approach in crop plants for overcoming the biotic and abiotic stresses by analysis of functional elements of the genome and explaining the components in the cell and tissues (Wang *et al.*, 2009). The transcriptome analysis is mainly done by three approaches *i.e.* RNA-seq, hybridization based and sequence based approaches (Tan *et al.*, 2009; Wang *et al.*, 2009). The transcriptome analysis of healthy and malformed tissues will help in understanding the expression of different stress related genes which would helpful in unraveling the complexity of the mango malformation disease.

In first part of the study, we discuss about the differential expressed transcripts (transcription factor, protein kinase, R-genes, flowering genes and phytohormone) and SSR markers in healthy and malformed tissues. The second part of our discussion includes the classification of differentially expressed genes in GO and KEGG pathways along with gene network analysis of defense related and phytohormone signaling genes. The discussion in third part of our study is dealt with in-silico analysis of *Fusarium* resistance genes. The outcomes of the present investigation are discussed under the following subheadings.

5.1 Differential expression of transcripts in malformed and healthy tissues.

5.1.1 *De novo* assembly, functional annotation, gene ontology (GO), comprehensive orthologs group (COG) analysis and SSR mining of transcripts in healthy and malformed tissues.

Sequences of all five different stages of malformed and healthy tissues were obtained using Illumina True-seq method. *De-novo* sequencing was used for the comparison of malformed and healthy tissues of mango variety Amarpali at different growth stages. The outcome of transcriptome analysis provide novel insights in a mango

tree physiology and molecular biology and offers an excellent platform for the discovery of new genes and molecular markers for the breeding of varieties resistant to mango malformation disease. The blast hit in our transcriptome data varied from 96.48 to 97.00% whereas in other mango cultivars (Langra, Tommy Atkins and Keitt) it varied from 60.62 to 98.2% (Azim *et al.*, 2014; Dautt-Castro *et al.*, 2015; Sherman *et al.*, 2015). Unigenes sequence matches were found with *Citrus sinensis*, *Citrus clementina*, *Theobroma cocoa*, *Jatropha curcas*, and *Vitis vinifera* and similar results were observed in different mango cultivars *i.e.* Shelly, Kent, Dashehari, Keitt (Luria *et al.*, 2014; Dautt-Castro *et al.*, 2015; Srivastava *et al.*, 2016; Liu *et al.*, 2016b). The initial GC content in healthy and malformed buds was more, which decreased in later stages of bud to panicle development. The decrease in GC content was higher in malformed buds, while in healthy buds it decreases very slightly at different growth stages. Mishra *et al.* (2009) had also observed high GC content among the stress regulated RNA sequences in *Arabidopsis thaliana* indicating that GC content play a crucial role for identification of stressed regulated miRNAs. Due to unavailability of sufficient genomic data in the dicot plants, the significance of GC content affects the evolution of plant species (Smarda, 2014). We observed that the GC content in Mango variety Amrapali was 39.94% which is nearer to GC content observed by Srivastava *et al.* (2016) in mango cv Dasherri (44.6%) and citrus (43.42 to 43.53%) by Guo *et al.* (2015).

GO analysis showed large numbers of unigenes in the biological process category, followed by cellular process and molecular function category. In biological process category; metabolic process, cellular process and single-organism process were dominant, while in metabolic process category; catalytic activity and binding represented the major proportion. In cellular process category; cell, cell part, organelle and membrane were the dominant classes. These results were similar to the findings of the Wang *et al.* (2012) in banana transcriptome and contradictory to the results of Liu *et al.* (2016b). COG analysis indicated that the percentage of unigenes in defense COG categories were more in healthy tissues (HB-1: 2.95%; HB-2: 2.92%) as compared to malformed tissues (MB-1: 2.84%; MB-2: 2.25% and MB-3: 2.23%).

5.1.2 SSR markers

SSRs are most commonly and extensively used molecular markers in plant breeding programs for determining genetic variations across species, due to high polymorphism rates, their high abundance, ease of development and broad distribution throughout the genome. We screened 426, 475, 517, 546 and 490 SSR makers at MB-1, MB-2, MB-3, HB-1 and HB-2 stages respectively which can be useful in the development of molecular markers for further studies related to taxonomy (Lagoda *et al.*, 1998), genetic diversity (Gupta *et al.*, 2003), marker assisted breeding, genetic map saturation (Hippolyte *et al.*, 2010), posttranscriptional and transcriptional regulatory functions (Tranbarger *et al.*, 2012) and large-scale genotyping (Christelova *et al.*, 2011). We identified maximum frequency of tri-nucleotide repeats (86.47%) followed by di-nucleotides (12.42%), tetra-nucleotide, hexa-nucleotide and penta-nucleotide. Similarly, Passo *et al.* (2013) in *Musa acuminata* and Du *et al.* (2015) in liliun, has observed higher number of trinucleotide repeats, followed by dinucleotide repeats.

5.1.3 Differentially expressed transcripts in malformed and healthy tissues

In transcriptome analysis, differential expression analysis means finding the genes or transcripts in different samples like healthy vs. disease, tissues or at different developmental stages. For differential expression analysis the transcripts must be expressed significantly in different quantities in distinct samples. The advantage of differential expression analysis is that it helps in knowing the phenotypic variation at molecular level. Earlier DNA microarrays were used to find the differential expressed genes. However nowadays, due to decrease in the cost of sequencing, RNA-sequencing is becoming most popular technique for differential expression analysis (Soneson and Delorenzi, 2013).

5.1.4 Differentially expressed transcripts of phytohormone

The differentially expressed genes were analyzed for different hormones (auxins, gibberellins, cytokinin, ABA and ethylene) in malformed and healthy tissues at different stages of bud development. In our study total up-regulated genes responsible for ethylene (7) are more in healthy tissues compared to the malformed tissues followed by auxin (6), GA (6), ABA (2) and cytokinin (1). The maximum down-regulated

phytohormone genes were observed for auxin (6), followed by ethylene (3) and cytokinin (1). Liu *et al.* (2016b) had also observed more number of up-regulated genes for ethylene in mango after artificial inoculation with *Fusarium* in mango.

5.1.5 Differential expressed transcripts of protein kinase genes

On differential expression analysis we observed that during bud stages (HB-1 vs MB-1) LRR receptor-like serine/threonine-protein kinase (6), putative receptor-like protein kinase (5 genes) had more up-regulated genes followed by serine/threonine-protein kinase (4); while at panicle development stages (HB-2 vs MB-3), two each proteins kinase related transcripts of LRR receptor-like serine/threonine-protein kinase, putative receptor-like protein kinase, CBL-interacting protein kinase, serine/threonine-protein kinase were up-regulated, indicating that these transcripts might play important role in resistance against *F. mangiferae* infection. CBL-interacting protein kinases along with calcineurin B-like proteins (CBLs) play an important role in stress signaling transduction and enhancing plant stress tolerance (Ye *et al.*, 2013; Tai *et al.*, 2016). LRR receptor-like serine/threonine-protein kinase, serine/threonine-protein kinase related transcripts were commonly downregulated at bud and panicle development stages. MAPKs play important role in response to a broad variety of biotic and abiotic stresses, including wounding, pathogen infection, temperature, drought, salinity, but also in the signaling of plant hormones and the cell division (Zhang *et al.*, 2006; Sun *et al.*, 2014). For development of resistance against pathogens MAPK cascade-mediated signaling is an essential step (Pitzschke *et al.*, 2009). Similarly, Liu *et al.* (2016b) had also observed DEG's related to LRR receptor-like serine/threonine-protein kinases, LRR protein kinases serine/threonine protein kinases, G-type lectin S-receptor-like serine threonine-protein kinases, cysteine-rich receptor-like protein kinases in *Fusarium mangiferae* infected Keitt cultivar of mango.

5.1.6 Differentially expressed transcripts related to flowering

The differential expression analysis of flowering genes showed that 48 genes were up-regulated and 41 genes were down-regulated. During bud stages (HB-1 vs MB-1), LDL2, TPL and WRKY were up-regulated whereas while at panicle development stages (HB-2 vs MB-3), UBP-12, MYB30, AGL-24 and early flowering genes (ELF,

EFS, REF6) were up-regulated. The TPL (Topless) flowering gene is responsible for controlling the abnormality in flowering, indicating that this transcript will play crucial role in solving the problem of malformation. Flowering is modulated and controlled by flowering genes and environmental signals (Walworth *et al.*, 2016) which is mainly affecting the mango malformation. In mango there is dearth of information on molecular basis of flowering which need to be extensively studied by investigating the networks of flowering and flowering related genes which will be helpful to overcome the mango malformation.

5.1.7 Differentially expressed transcription factors

Transcription factors (TFs) are DNA binding proteins which are sequence specific in nature and play a crucial role in various biological process (cell differentiation, cell development, transcriptional regulation and physiological response) in plants (Wunderlich and Mirny, 2009; Spitz and Furlong, 2012). They represent the multigene family which interact with cis-elements found in promoter region of the gene and they change its expression by enhancing or repressing its expression pattern (Davies and Schwinn, 2003). We observed that maximum transcription factors up-regulated were of WRKY (12), followed by ERF (6), and MYB (5) indicating that WRKY, ERF and MYB transcription factors might be responsible for resistance against mango malformation. MYB TF family is large and varied from 64 to 100 copies. It is involved in controlling various processes like responses to biotic and abiotic stresses (Dubos *et al.*, 2010). The expression of TF's *i.e.* AP2-EREBP, ARF, BES1, Bhlh, bZIP, C2C2-GATA, C2H2, E2F-DP, FAR1, OFP, Orphans, PLATZ, SBP, Sigma70-like and TAZ were high in healthy tissues compared to malformed tissues which might be indicating their role in avoiding the susceptibility to mango malformation. The major category of transcription factor in our study are in accordance to the transcriptomic results of the *Arachis hypogaea* (Guimaraes *et al.*, 2012), *Chrysanthemum morifolium* (Xu *et al.*, 2013) and *Sophora moorcroftiana* (Li *et al.*, 2015). The identified TF's are having important roles in development, differentiation, metabolism, defenses and in controlling various biotic and abiotic stresses.

5.1.8 Differentially expressed transcripts related to resistance genes or proteins

Plants have evolved several resistance genes (R-genes) or proteins whose products mediate resistance to various biotic and abiotic stresses. In our study 26 DEG's were observed in mango transcriptome with 16 transcripts up-regulated and 10 transcripts down-regulated. Among R-genes, RPM-1, TMV, RGA-3, pleotropic disease resistance and NB-ARC domain containing disease resistance protein were significantly expressed. Resistant genes/proteins allow pathogen effectors recognition through direct binding or by alteration of a host protein (Jones and Dangl, 2006).

5.2 Functional annotations, pathway and gene networks of the differentially expressed genes (DEGs)

5.2.1 Pathway analysis of transcripts in healthy and malformed tissues

The KEGG pathway analysis indicated maximum number of unigenes sequences under signal transduction, followed by translation, carbohydrate metabolism, amino acid metabolism. These results are similar to finding of Wang *et al.* (2012) in banana root transcriptome under *Fusarium oxysporum* infection and contradictory to the findings of Liu *et al.* (2016b) who reported maximum number of transcripts in ribosome pathway followed by oxidative phosphorylation and protein processing in endoplasmic reticulum in mango transcriptome.

5.2.2 Biosynthesis of secondary metabolite pathways

Secondary metabolites (SMs) are the low molecular weight organic compounds (molecular mass < 3000 Ds) which are not involved in plant growth and development like primary metabolite (Andersson, 2012; Scharf *et al.*, 2014). The fungi and plant are abundant source of SMs. The SMs produced by fungi act as antifungal, antiviral, antibacterial and anti-tumour (Keller *et al.*, 2005). Their production in plants after pathogen attack is positively correlated with the disease resistance and also varies according to genera to genera and species to species. The transcripts related to different pathways *i.e.* “phenylpropanoid biosynthesis”, “flavonoid biosynthesis”, “tropane, piperidine and pyridine alkaloid biosynthesis”, “isoquinoline alkaloid biosynthesis”, “stilbenoid, diarylheptanoid and gingerol biosynthesis”, “streptomycin biosynthesis”, “monobactam biosynthesis” and “butirosin and neomycin biosynthesis” were higher in

healthy buds (HB-1) compared to single swollen malformed buds (MB-1); whereas transcripts related to “anthocyanin biosynthesis”, “isoflavonoid biosynthesis”, “betalain biosynthesis” and “novobiocin biosynthesis” were slightly more in single swollen malformed buds (MB-1) compared to healthy buds (HB-1). The biosynthesis of secondary metabolite pathways were significantly enriched after pathogen attack in banana infected with *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. cubense tropical race 4 (Li *et al.*, 2012; Bai *et al.*, 2013) and in *Fusarium verticillioides* infected maize genotypes (Lanubile *et al.*, 2014). We observed that most numbers of the transcripts as well as number of differentially expressed transcripts were related to “phenylpropanoid biosynthesis” and “flavonoid biosynthesis” pathways indicating their important roles in resistance against malformation. Similarly Liu *et al.*, (2016b) observed that “phenylpropanoid biosynthesis” and “flavonoid biosynthesis” pathway transcripts were significantly enriched in mango cv. Kiett infected with *Fusarium mangiferae*.

5.2.3 Plant pathogen interaction pathway

Several interaction studies on plant and pathogen have been studied in context of plant as well as pathogen. In the present era of genomics, transcriptomic analysis of plant pathogen interaction pathway helps in finding proteins or genes related to defense and pathogenicity. The pathways provides better understanding of molecular mechanism in plant, by providing the information how a pathogen and plant recognize each other and how they establish a positive or negative relationship (Mehta *et al.*, 2008). Therefore we performed the transcript profiling of healthy and malformed tissues for plant pathogen interaction pathways. Our results indicated that number of transcripts as well as differentially expressed genes of calcium binding protein CML were highly expressed in healthy buds (HB-1 and HB-2) indicating that it might play crucial role in malformation resistance. Similarly calcium binding protein CML was also significantly enriched in cucumber infected *Botrytis cinerea* (Kong *et al.*, 2015) and tomato lines infected with on *Xanthomonas perforans* Race T3 (Du *et al.*, 2015).

5.2.4 Signaling transduction pathways

In plants there are mainly two types of innate immune system *i.e.* PTI (PAMP-triggered immunity) and ETI (Effector-triggered immunity). To overcome the PAMP-triggered immunity and Effector-triggered immunity, pathogen secretes effector

molecules. The signaling pathways play important role in defense response by mediating signaling and transcriptional reprogramming through MAPK cascades and WRKY transcription factors respectively (Jones and Dangl, 2006). Genetic analysis of signaling pathway genes in future will provide ample scope in crop improvement programme. Besides this, among phyto-hormones; signaling of ethylene, jasmonic acid and salicylic acid pathways plays most prominent role in defense. Several reports on auxin, gibberellin, cytokinin, abscisic acid and brassinosteroids signaling for defense response were made earlier (Kazan and Manners, 2009; Pieterse *et al.*, 2012; Qin *et al.*, 2013; Alazem *et al.*, 2014). Our results indicated that in healthy buds number of transcripts and differentially expressed transcripts were enriched in “plant hormone signal transduction”, Ras signaling pathway” and “hedgehog signaling pathway” and “AMPK signaling pathway”, “MAPK signaling pathway”, and “VEGF signaling pathway” were more expressed in malformed buds.

5.2.5 Carbohydrate metabolic pathway

Carbohydrate metabolic pathway plays a crucial role in plant defense by inducing the PR related genes. In our study we observed more numbers of differential expressed transcripts related to “amino sugar and nucleotide sugar metabolism”, “glyoxylate and dicarboxylate metabolism” “glycolysis/gluconeogenesis”, and “ascorbate and aldarate metabolism” pathways in healthy buds (HB-1 and HB-2) compared to malformed buds (MB-1 and MB-3). Similarly, Less *et al.* (2011) observed that pentose phosphate pathway and TCA cycle of carbohydrate metabolic pathway are involved in energy production due to which more number transcripts were up-regulated in response to different stresses.

5.2.6 Amino acid pathway

In present era of genomics, metabolomics and transcriptomic approaches play crucial roles in deciphering the role of amino acid and their pathways in plant defense. It has been observed that pathogen attack in plants leads to accumulation of several amino acids which protects the plants from biotic and abiotic stresses. Hence we focused in our study on the different amino acid pathways and observed that the numbers of differentially expressed transcripts related to “phenylalanine metabolism”, “arginine and

proline metabolism”, “lysine degradation”, “alanine, aspartate and glutamate metabolism”, “phenylalanine, tyrosine and tryptophan biosynthesis”, “cysteine and methionine metabolism” and “glycine, serine and threonine metabolism” were more in healthy buds (HB-1 and HB-2) compared to malformed buds (MB-1 and MB-3). Similarly, by using transcriptomic approach in *P. syringae* infected arabidopsis (Scheideler *et al.*, 2002; Ward *et al.*, 2010) and tomato (Less *et al.*, 2011) infected *P. syringae* showed accumulation of various amino acids (valine, leucine, isoleucine, threonine, alanine, phenylalanine, tyrosine, glutamine and tyrosine) and upregulation of various amino acid transcripts.

5.2.7 Energy metabolism pathways

Energy production pathways also have significant roles in maintaining the plant defense by producing enough level of energy. Therefore we analyzed energy metabolism pathway in healthy and malformed tissues and found that maximum number of transcripts were observed for “oxidative phosphorylation”, and “methane metabolism” pathways in healthy buds (HB-1 vs MB-1) compared to malformed buds (HB-2 and MB-3). However, higher numbers of transcripts related to “oxidative phosphorylation” were differentially expressed in healthy buds (HB-1 and HB-2) compared to malformed buds (MB-1 and MB-3). Similarly, “oxidative phosphorylation” related transcripts were also significantly expressed in transcriptome of tomato affected with *Verticillium dahlia* (Tan *et al.*, 2015), mango infected with *Fusarium mangiferae* (Liu *et al.*, 2016b).

5.2.8 Lipid metabolism pathways

The different lipid metabolism related pathways play paramount roles in controlling the biotic and abiotic stresses by providing energy to the cell and maintaining the structure of cell membrane and cell wall (Welti, 2007). Various processes in the cell such as fate of cell, cell growth, cell differentiation, membrane trafficking, signal transduction and cytoskeletal rearrangements are maintained through different types of lipids present in plants (Wang *et al.*, 2004; Welti, 2007). Our results on lipid metabolism pathway indicated more differentially expressed transcripts in healthy bud (HB-1) compared to single swollen malformed bud (MB-1). Tan *et al.*

(2015) observed differentially expressed transcripts related to “lipid transport and metabolism” in tomato infected with *Verticillium dahlia* transcriptome.

5.2.9 Phytohormone signaling pathway related transcripts

Phyto-hormones such as auxin, gibberellin, cytokinin, abscisic acid, ethylene, salicylic acid, jasmonic acid controls various different endogenous and exogenous cues/ stimulus which helps in controlling the various development process in plants during its life cycle (Quecini *et al.*, 2007; Rigal and Ma, 2014). They also play important roles in plant-pathogen interactions (Fu and Wang, 2011). The plant hormones which play crucial roles in governing the plant defense are ethylene, jasmonic acid and salicylic acid (Kunkel and Brooks, 2002; Genger *et al.*, 2008).

Our results showed higher numbers of transcripts for auxin signaling genes (AUX-IAA), abscisic acid (ABF), brassinosteroid (BSK) in healthy buds (HB-1 and HB-2) compared to malformed buds (MB-1 and MB-3). The differentially expressed transcripts for hormone signaling revealed higher numbers of signaling gene *i.e.* SAUR (auxin) and ABF (abscisic acid) in both healthy buds (HB-1 and HB-2) compared to malformed buds (MB-1 and MB-2). Several physiological studies reported lower levels of auxin in malformed tissues compare to healthy tissues (Dashan, 1987; Pandey, 1988; Dhillon and Singh, 1989) indicating that development of healthy panicles may be due to increased levels of auxins. Our transcriptomic findings on auxin concentration are in confirmation with the physiological studies reported earlier in healthy and malformed tissues (Dashan, 1987; Pandey, 1988; Dhillon and Singh, 1989).

5.2.10 Network analysis of differentially expressed defense genes

The protein-protein interaction analysis between mango defense genes and orthologs of *vitis vinifera* inferred that HSP (heat shock protein), SHMT (serine hydroxy-methyltransferase), SOD (superoxide dismutase), WRKY 33, MAPK (mitogen-activated protein kinases), CCR (cinnamoyl CoA reductase), and LHY5 (late elongated hypocotyl) were actively involved defense genes in mango malformation, whereas between mango and *Populus trichocarpa*, SHMT (serine hydroxy-methyltransferase), SOD (superoxide dismutase), WRKY 33 (2), MAPK (mitogen-activated protein kinases), CCR (cinnamoyl CoA reductase) and LHY5 (late

elongated hypocotyl) were more actively present in protein interaction network. In healthy buds at different growth stages, HSP were more actively involved in protein-protein-interaction network with *Vitis vinifera* and *Populus trichocarpa* followed by other defense genes namely SHMT, SOD, WRKY 33, MAPK, CCR and LHY5. Similar results for HSP (heat shock proteins) were also observed in sweet orange protein-protein interaction network (Ding *et al.*, 2014).

5.2.11 Network analysis of phytohormone signaling pathways genes

The results of orthologs of phytohormone signaling pathway genes indicated that all genes were of auxin hormone in gene network. Among the hormone signaling pathway genes, the 55 orthologs belonged to all three malformed stages *i.e.* single swollen malformed bud stage I (MB-1), multiple malformed bud stage 2 (MB-2), multiple malformed panicle development stage 3 (MB-3). Several physiological studies also revealed about the high level of auxin in malformed stages compare to healthy stages, indicating that auxin plays crucial role in mango malformation (Abou-Hussein *et al.*, 1975; Rajan, 1986; Chakrabarti *et al.*, 1990).

5.3. In-silico analysis of *Fusarium* resistance genes of different plant species

5.3.1 Homologous gene sequence between mango and *Fusarium* species

Causation of malformation in mango by *Fusarium* species is an outcome of interactive regulation of both mango (*Mangifera indica* L.) and *Fusarium* genes. In malformed tissues of mango, genes having similarity with *Fusarium fujikurui* (causes bakane disease in rice) were higher, when compared with other fungal species. This was because *F. mangiferae* is phylogenetically closely related to *F. fujikurui* (Wiemann *et al.*, 2013). However one transcripts was observed at MB-1 and MB-3 because complete gene sequence data of *F. mangiferae* was not published. However visible disease symptoms caused by *F. mangiferae* and *F. fujikurui* are distinctly opposite. In bakane disease, infected seedlings exhibit abnormal elongation, where as in mango malformation, there is reduction in the length of the primary axis and secondary branches of the panicle, characterized by appreciably reduced internodes, giving the appearance of a witches-broom. The number of *Fusarium* related transcripts were 1.5 to 2 times higher in malformed buds compared to healthy buds indicating that

malformation is caused by *Fusarium* species. Out of 14 species, the transcripts related to *F. fujikurii*, *F. proliferatum*, *F. oxysporium* and *F. mangiferae* sequences were higher in malformed buds compared to healthy buds at different growth stages indicating their role in causation of malformation (Bhatnagar and Beniwal, 1977; Zhan *et al.*, 2012; Nor *et al.*, 2013; Joshi *et al.*, 2014).

5.3.2 Physico-chemical properties of *Fusarium* resistance genes

Fusarium resistance genes are highly polymorphic and have wide recognition specificities due to gene duplication, genomic forces (insertion, deletion etc.) and constant selection pressure by pathogen evolution. This leads to slow progress in development of *Fusarium* disease resistant varieties. Protein information of *Fusarium* resistance genes can be used in identification of homologs in different plant genomes, preservation of the genetic code, trans-membrane alpha-helices of membrane proteins and also to measure the hydrophobicity of a specific peptide/protein in the sample. Out of 65 *Fusarium* resistance gene sequences studied, 33 protein sequences were stable in nature with pI of protein value ranging from 4.17 to 11.12. Protein pI is having an important role in finding the pH dependent characteristics of a protein (Talley and Alexov, 2010). The pI of protein is the pH at which the protein does not carry a net-charge and its value is obtained by the number of protonatable and deprotonatable side chains (Garcia-Moreno, 2009). The instability index of the protein sequences describes whether the protein is stable or not. Our studies revealed GRAVY score that ranged from -0.507 (NBS-16) to 0.898 (CHS-7). Similar reports were made earlier by other workers (Zhao and London, 2006; Crasto, 2010; Mallikarjuna *et al.*, 2016).

5.3.3 Protein binding sites and hydrophobicity analysis of protein sequence

Protein binding site is region in a protein on which specific molecules/ions attach to form a chemical bond. The binding sites are more active sites in proteins which are mainly of hydrophobic in nature and also plays an important role in the interaction specificity (Labute and Santavy, 2007; Stank *et al.*, 2016). The information on protein binding sites and receptor functionalities in horticultural crops is still lacking. It is necessary to understand the distribution pattern of hydrophobicity in protein sequences and structures because hydrophobicity plays an important role in development of protein

structures (Sandelin, 2004). The knowledge of hydrophobicity will be helpful in the studying the important information regarding protein folding, prediction of trans-membrane sequences and water-protein-lipid interaction. We observed that distribution pattern for binding site is more, while hydrophobicity is very low to low in five genes namely beta-glucanase, I-2-clone-2942, I-7, chit-42 and NBS-15. Our findings on hydrophobicity of protein sequences show potential to find the crystallographic determinations of each binding sites and offers possibilities for developing varieties resistant to *Fusarium* diseases in different crops.

5.3.4 Conserved domain search and Trans-membrane prediction

The GH18 (glycoside hydrolase18) domain was found in β -glucanase gene. GH18 is a multigene family of chitinases which plays various roles in embryonic development and allergic inflammation (Huang *et al.*, 2012). NB-ARC domain was found in NBS-15 gene. In the disease resistance genes or proteins, the NB-ARC present in NBS-15 gene is mostly conserved domain which acts as molecular switch in resistance proteins to help the plant against biotic and abiotic stresses (Pal *et al.*, 2007; Van *et al.*, 2008). In our results, two of the genes (chit-42 and NBS-15) are having multi-domain proteins. These multiple domain proteins are highly stable and have benefits in terms of folding compared to single domain proteins in the cell as reported by Bhaskara *et al.*, (2011). The conserved domains namely GH18, NB-ARC, LRR-RI, P-loop NTPase superfamily and Glyco-18 present in resistance genes are independently stable sequences which can be used to develop chimeric proteins through genetic engineering for crop improvement. Protein domain dynamics play crucial roles for molecular recognition and signaling processes in cells. In our results, trans-membrane helix was present in I-7 gene, while it was absent in rest of four genes. Trans-membrane proteins in the resistance genes regulate the information and other different substances from inside and outside of the cell and are actively involved in a various other biological processes (Reynolds *et al.*, 2008).

5.3.5 Multiple Sequence Alignment and Phylogenetic Analysis

Multiple sequence alignment (MSA) is becoming powerful tool in plant science for estimating phylogenetic reconstruction, illuminating functionally important regions,

structure prediction of proteins (secondary and tertiary structure), protein function, structure of RNAs (Kemena and Notredame, 2009), biological function analysis and performing the task of next-generation sequencing (Ortuno *et al.*, 2013). MSA of different *Fusarium* resistant genes will be helpful in knowing the binding sites, active sites and conserved domains. The phylogenetic analysis of *Fusarium* resistance genes presented in group A (I2 clone 2956) showed more similar conserved motif pattern with group B (I2 clone 3333, I2 clone 2958, I2 clone 2950, I2 clone 3324, I2 clone 3336 and I2 clone 2942) followed by subgroup C1 and C3. Evolutionary forces probably caused these changes during evolutionary processes. Subgroup C2 was unique as compared to other groups and subgroups which could be due to some genomic forces (insertion, deletion etc.) which might affect the different *Fusarium* resistance gene structures.

5.3.6 Motif prediction

The motif analysis indicated that motif-3 and motif-1 are most commonly occurring motifs among *Fusarium* resistance gene sequences. Motifs information can be used for developing resistance genes and makers, to perform clustering (Broin *et al.*, 2015), gene expression analysis study (Jensen *et al.*, 2005, Huber and Bulyk, 2006) and discovery of homology relations (Stewart, 2016), family classification (Blekas *et al.*, 2005; Eser *et al.*, 2013), discovery of sub-families in large protein families (Leonardi and Galves, 2005) and new signaling pathways (Ma *et al.*, 2013). The statistical significance of motif prediction was also correlated with biological significance, indicating a valuable reason for the motifs analysis (Zhang *et al.*, 2009). Phylogenetic tree results were in agreement with the results of conserved motif analysis.

5.3.7 Cis-regulatory elements

The spatial and temporal differences in gene expression levels of an organism are the results of interactions between DNA, RNA and protein. DNA *cis*-regulatory elements consist of promoters, enhancers and insulators which play important roles in gene regulation process (Fiedler and Rehmsmeier, 2006; Ibraheem *et al.*, 2010; Himani *et al.*, 2014). We also observed various *cis*-regulatory elements *i.e.* TC-rich repeats, Box-W1, EIRE, AT-rich sequence, CGTCA-motif; TGACG-motif which play crucial roles against *Fusarium* induced diseases in various horticultural crops. Our studies showed

that Box-W1 *cis*-regulatory element is *Fusarium* elicitor responsive and provides insights in the *evolution of Fusarium* resistance genes. So to understand the gene regulation process and the development process of organisms the knowledge of *cis*-regulatory elements is indispensable. The identification of these CRE and their CREs across species will allow an understanding of the diversity, distribution and evolutionary relationships of these genes (Wittkopp and Kalay, 2012; Lemmon *et al.*, 2014; Hernandez-Garcia and Finer, 2014).

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

**The whole point of this sentence is to
make clear what the whole point of this
sentence is**

-Douglas R. Hofstadter

The present investigation entitled “**Identification of genes associated with mango malformation through Differential Expression Analysis**” was carried out in mango variety Amrapali at Division of Fruits and Horticultural Technology, ICAR-Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi. Transcriptomic approach (RNA-Seq) approach was used for generating a wealth of data on the genes associated with mango malformation disease. The results of the present investigations are summarized below.

- The alignment of unigene sequences of mango malformed and healthy samples with NR database showed top matches with *Citrus sinensis*, *Citrus clementina* and *Theobroma cocoa*.
- Out of 1,52,807 unigenes sequences, 147,832 (96.74%) were annotated through NR database, 79,895 (52.28%) were annotated through gene ontology analysis and 44,982 (29.44%) were annotated through COG analysis.
- Differential expression analysis of phytohormone revealed that total up-regulated genes responsible for ethylene (7) are more in healthy tissues compared to the malformed tissues followed by auxin (6), GA (6), ABA (2) and cytokinin (1). The maximum down-regulated phytohormone genes were observed for auxin (6), followed by ethylene (3) and cytokinin (1).
- During bud stages (HB-1 vs MB-1), the differential expression analysis revealed that LRR receptor-like serine/threonine-protein kinase (6), putative receptor-like protein kinase (5 genes) had more up-regulated genes followed by serine/threonine-protein kinase (4); while at panicle development stages (HB-2 vs MB-3), two each proteins kinase related transcripts of LRR receptor-like serine/threonine-protein kinase, putative receptor-like protein kinase, CBL-interacting protein kinase, serine/threonine-protein kinase were up-regulated, indicating that these transcripts might play important role in resistance against *F. mangiferae* infection.
- The differential expression analysis of flowering genes showed that 48 genes were up-regulated and 41 genes were down-regulated. During bud stages (HB-1 vs MB-1), LDL2, TPL and WRKY were up-regulated whereas at panicle development stages (HB-

2 vs MB-3), UBP-12, MYB30, AGL-24 and early flowering genes (ELF, EFS, REF6) were up-regulated.

- We observed that maximum transcription factor up-regulated were of WRKY (12), followed by ERF (6), and MYB (5) indicating that WRKY, ERF and MYB transcription factors might be responsible for resistance against mango malformation.
- In our study 26 DEG's were observed in mango transcriptome with 16 transcripts up-regulated and 10 transcripts down-regulated. Among R-genes, RPM-1, TMV, RGA-3, pleotropic disease resistance and NB-ARC domain containing disease resistance protein were significantly expressed.
- Among the 207 KEGG pathways, highest number of transcripts fell under metabolism, followed by genetic information processing, environmental information processing, cellular processes and organismal system.
- Analysis of biosynthesis of secondary metabolite pathways revealed that number of differentially expressed transcripts related to “phenylpropanoid biosynthesis” and “flavonoid biosynthesis” pathways were more in single swollen malformed bud stage (MB-1) compared to healthy bud stage (HB-1) indicating their role in resistance against malformation.
- Our results on plant pathogen interaction pathways indicated that number of transcripts as well as differentially expressed genes of calcium binding protein CML were highly expressed in healthy buds (HB-1 and HB-2) indicating that it might play crucial role in malformation resistance.
- Signaling transduction pathway results indicated that in healthy buds at different growth stages, number of transcripts and differentially expressed transcripts were enriched in “plant hormone signal transduction”, “Ras signaling pathway” and “hedgehog signaling pathway”, whereas “AMPK signaling pathway”, “MAPK signaling pathway” and “VEGF signaling pathway” were more expressed in malformed buds at different growth stages.
- In our study we observed that the number of differential expressed transcripts related to carbohydrate metabolic pathways i.e. “amino sugar & nucleotide sugar metabolism”, “glyoxylate and dicarboxylate metabolism” “glycolysis/ gluconeogenesis” and “ascorbate and aldarate metabolism” were more in healthy buds at different growth

stages (HB-1 and HB-2) compared to malformed buds at different growth stages (MB-1 and MB-3).

- The results on amino acid pathway analysis revealed that the number of differentially expressed transcripts related to “phenylalanine metabolism”, “arginine and proline metabolism”, “lysine degradation”, “alanine, aspartate and glutamate metabolism”, “phenylalanine, tyrosine and tryptophan biosynthesis”, “cysteine and methionine metabolism” and “glycine, serine and threonine metabolism” were more in healthy buds (HB-1 and HB-2) compared to malformed buds (MB-1 and MB-3).
- Energy production pathways also have significant role in maintaining the plant defense by producing enough level of energy. Therefore we analyzed energy metabolism pathway in healthy and malformed tissues and found that maximum number of transcripts were observed for “oxidative phosphorylation”, and “methane metabolism” pathways in healthy buds (HB-1 vs MB-1) compared to malformed buds at different growth stages (HB-2 and MB-3). However, higher numbers of transcripts related to “oxidative phosphorylation” were differentially expressed in healthy buds at different growth stages (HB-1 and HB-2) compared to malformed buds at different growth stages (MB-1 and MB-3).
- Our results indicate that higher numbers of transcripts were observed for auxin signaling genes (AUX-IAA), abscisic acid (ABF), brassinosteroid (BSK) in healthy buds at different growth stages (HB-1 and HB-2) compared to malformed buds at different growth stages (MB-1 and MB-3). The differentially expressed transcripts of hormone signaling revealed that signaling gene *i.e.* SAUR (auxin) and ABF (abscisic acid) were higher in both healthy (HB-1 and HB-2) and malformed (MB-1 and MB-2) buds at different growth stages.
- Gene networking analysis of differentially expressed genes inferred that HSP (heat shock protein), SHMT (serine hydroxy-methyltransferase), SOD (superoxide dismutase), WRKY 33, MAPK (mitogen-activated protein kinases), CCR (cinnamoyl CoA reductase), and LHY5 (late elongated hypocotyl) were actively involved defense genes in mango malformation.
- Gene networking analysis of differentially expressed phytohormone signaling pathway genes indicated that in gene network all genes observed were of auxin. Out of 55

orthologs related to signaling pathway, all were from the three malformed stages *i.e.* single swollen malformed bud stage 1 (MB-1), multiple malformed bud stage 2 (MB-2) and malformed panicle development stage 3 (MB-3).

- The number of *Fusarium* related transcripts were 1.5 to 2 times higher in malformed buds (MB-1: 219, MB-1: 164 and MB-3: 236) compared to healthy buds (HB-1:129 and HB-2:99) at different growth stages indicating that malformation is caused by *Fusarium* species. Our study on 14 *Fusarium* species revealed that the transcripts related to *F. fujikurii*, *F. proliferatum*, *F. oxysporium* and *F. mangiferae* sequences were higher in malformed buds compared to healthy buds at different growth stages indicating that malformation is a disease caused by *Fusarium* species.
- Out of 65 *Fusarium* resistance gene sequences studied, 33 protein sequences were stable in nature with pI of protein value ranging from 4.17 to 11.12. The distribution pattern for binding site is more, while hydrophobicity is very low to low in five genes namely beta-glucanase, I-2-clone-2942, I-7, chit-42 and NBS-15. The results on hydrophobicity of protein sequences show potential to find the crystallographic determinations of each binding sites and offers possibilities for developing varieties resistant to *Fusarium* diseases in different crops.
- The GH18 (glycoside hydrolase18) domain was found in β -glucanase gene whereas NB-ARC domain was found in NBS-15 gene. In the disease resistance genes or proteins, the NB-ARC present in NBS-15 gene is mostly conserved domain which acts as molecular switch in resistant proteins to help the plant against biotic and abiotic stresses. In our results, two of the genes (chit-42 and NBS-15) are having multi-domain proteins. The conserved domains namely GH18, NB-ARC, LRR-RI, P-loop NTPase superfamily and Glyco-18 present in resistance genes are independently stable sequences which can be used to develop chimeric proteins through genetic engineering for crop improvement. The trans-membrane helix was present in I-7 gene, while it was absent in rest of four genes.
- Motif analysis in 65 *Fusarium* resistance genes indicated that motif-3 and motif-1 are most commonly occurring motif which can be used for developing resistance genes and markers to perform clustering gene expression analysis study and discovery of homology relations, family classifications, discovery of sub-families in large protein families and

new signaling pathways. Phylogenetic tree results were in agreement with the results of conserved motif analysis.

- The 92 types of *cis*-regulatory elements observed in 65 *Fusarium* resistance genes were categorized in different function categories *i.e.* light responsive, hormone responsive, biotic stress, abiotic stress, binding related and plant development process. Our results indicate that *Fusarium* elicitor responsive CRE's (Box-W1 and EIRE) and biotic stress responsive CRE's (TC-rich repeats, CGTCA-motif, AT-rich sequence and TGACG-motif) were more in *Fusarium* resistance genes.

Conclusion

The results from present study on identification of genes associated with mango malformation through differential expression analysis revealed that several genes related to plant hormones, flowering, transcription factors and protein kinases were associated with mango malformation. These findings will serve as foundation for future functional studies and mango improvement programmes in relation to mango malformation. Further, *in-silico* analysis revealed the homology of 65 *Fusarium* resistance genes. The physico-chemical properties of protein information of these *Fusarium* resistance genes can be used in identification of homologs in different plant genomes. Knowledge of functional analyses of phylogenetic study, *cis*-acting elements and motif prediction generated from this study will give better understanding of the transcriptional gene regulation system. It is essential to decipher the expression of these resistance genes, *cis-regulatory* elements and markers in economically important horticultural crops to improve disease resistance. The 3D structure of 5 stable *Fusarium* genes can be effectively used for *in silico* docking study for development of potential ligand molecules against *Fusarium* infection. The results can pave the way to develop highly resistance genotypes through development of molecular markers or gene specific markers. The genes identified from the present study need to be validated through RT-PCR prior to its usage in mango breeding programmes.

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**No scientific endeavor is a result of an
individual effect**

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APPENDICES

Annexure

Table 1 Quantification of RNA using Qubit Fluorometer

Samples	Concentration (ng/μl)	Volume (μl)	Yield (μg)	A _{260/280} (Determined from NanoDrop-8000)
MB-1	167	30	5	1.8
MB-2	478	30	14.3	2.1
MB-3	812	30	24.3	2.1
HB-1	1608	30	48.2	2.1
HB-2	1648	30	49.4	2.1

Table 2 List of software used in transcriptomic analysis of data.

Software	Use
Trimmomatic (V-0.30) software	Used to filter Illumina reads
Bridger	Assemble the transcripts
CD-Hit	Convert assembled transcripts into unigenes
Transdecoder	Prediction of CDS from the unigenes using Transdecoder
Blast2GO PRO	GO Analysis
COGNITOR	COG analysis
KAAS	KEGG pathway analysis
DESeq package	deferentially expressed (DE) genes
MISA	SSR Identification
Phyre2 server	Use to make 3D structure of proteins
PROCHECK software	Use to verify-3D structure of proteins
ProSA-web tool	Estimation Z-score of proteins
Discovery studio 3.5 visualizer tools	Binding sites and hydrophobicity analysis
CD-Search tool	Predict conserved domains proteins
MEGA 7.0	Construction of phylogenetic tree
CLUSTALW	Multiple sequence alignment of the identified resistant genes
MEME 4.10.2	Motif prediction
PlantCARE	CRE's prediction
ProtParam ExPASy	physico-chemical properties analysis of proteins
STRING	Network analysis
Cytoscape	Visualization of network analysis

Table 3 List of various *Fusarium* resistance genes and their physico-chemical properties

Gene source	Gene	GenBank ID	PL	Mol. Wt.	pI.	I.I.	GRAVY
<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>							
Petunia	PhDef-1	AF507975.1	103	11361.4	6.54	49.77	0.265
Petunia	PhDef1-(2)	HQ694498.1	103	11349.3	6.54	47.90	0.215
Petunia	PhDef-2	AF507976.1	101	11049.0	5.16	50.94	0.176
Lilium	Lr14-3-3	KF362120.1	259	29301.0	4.79	49.57	-0.459
<i>F. oxysporum f. sp. Vasinfectum</i>							
Cotton	NaD-1	AF509566.1	105	11721.9	6.56	61.25	0.137
<i>Fusarium oxysporum f. sp. Cubense</i>							
Banana	MusaBAG-1	KJ636053.1	152	16834.5	9.10	42.23	-0.375
Banana	NBS-2	KF034946.1	174	19426.3	5.49	43.77	-0.236
Banana	NBS-3	KF034947.1	174	19353.3	5.78	45.68	-0.286
Banana	NBS-4	KF034948.1	174	19478.4	5.78	48.97	-0.268
Banana	NBS-5	KF034949.1	174	19620.5	6.20	55.70	-0.351
Banana	NBS-6	KF034950.1	174	19537.4	5.78	55.99	-0.294
Banana	NBS-7	KF034951.1	174	19601.5	5.78	51.10	-0.326
Banana	NBS-8	KF034952.1	174	19569.5	5.78	56.48	-0.307
Banana	NBS-9	KF034953.1	174	19510.4	5.78	57.10	-0.279
Banana	NBS-10	KF034954.1	174	19537.4	5.78	55.99	-0.294
Banana	NBS-11	KF034955.1	174	19537.4	5.78	55.99	-0.294
Banana	NBS-12	KF034956.1	174	19537.4	5.78	55.99	-0.294
Banana	NBS-13	KF034957.1	174	19537.4	5.78	55.99	-0.294
Banana	NBS-14	KF034958.1	174	19569.5	5.78	56.48	-0.307
Banana	NBS-15	KF034959.1	178	20113.9	6.84	39.15	-0.458
Banana	NBS-16	KF034960.1	212	24338.0	7.10	47.83	-0.507
Yeast	CHS-7	NM-001179272.1	316	34898.2	5.46	23.31	0.898
<i>Fusarium oxysporum f. sp. Cubense race 1</i>							
Onion	Ace-AMP-1	AF004946.1	132	15141.9	11.12	50.39	0.017
<i>Trichoderma</i>	chit-42	S78423.1	423	46056.5	7.01	23.57	-0.311
Soybean	beta1,3-glucanase	AF034106.1	246	26992.5	4.52	31.12	0.074
<i>Fusarium oxysporum f. sp. Cubense race 4</i>							
Rice	Tlp	XM-015763091.1	177	17992.1	5.07	43.10	0.185
<i>Fusarium oxysporum f.sp. matthioli (FOM)</i>							
Arabidopsis	RFO-1	DQ023268.1	749	83435.4	6.43	44.85	0.200
<i>Fusarium oxysporum f.sp. melonis</i>							
Melon	Fom-2-PII61375	AY619649.1	533	61579.9	8.45	49.13	-0.214
Melon	Fom-2 (Ananas Yokneum)	AY619648.1	533	61611.8	8.04	47.99	-0.211
Melon	Fom-2 (Vedrantais)	AY619647.1	533	61611.8	8.04	47.99	-0.211
Melon	Fom-2 (Durango)	AY619646.1	533	61611.8	8.04	47.99	-0.211
Melon	Fom-2 protein gene (Partial cds)	AY619650.1	554	63811.1	7.29	45.64	-0.231

Melon	Fom-2 protein gene (Complete cds)	DQ287965.1	1073	123571.8	7.13	43.42	-0.193
<i>Fusarium oxysporum f. sp. Lycopersici (Fol) races 1, 2 and</i>							
Tomato	I-2 (clone 3318)	DQ205979.1	242	27159.3	7.64	32.40	-0.291
Tomato	I-2 (clone 2949)	DQ205977.1	242	27113.3	8.32	30.89	-0.240
Tomato	I-2 (clone3325)	DQ205976.1	242	27113.3	8.32	30.89	-0.240
Tomato	I-2 (clone-2950)	DQ205975.1	233	25999.9	6.86	28.72	-0.299
Tomato	I-2 (clone-3324)	DQ205974.1	241	27017.0	6.43	33.51	-0.299
Tomato	I-2 (clone-2942)	DQ205973.1	238	26643.7	7.64	28.50	-0.267
Tomato	I-2 (clone-3333)	DQ205972.1	243	27315.5	7.64	32.31	-0.283
Tomato	I-2 (clone-2957)	DQ205971.1	243	27315.5	7.64	32.31	-0.283
Tomato	I-2 (clone-3323)	DQ205970.1	243	27401.6	7.64	31.31	-0.300
Tomato	I-2 (clone-3335)	DQ205969.1	243	27368.5	8.41	33.65	-0.312
Tomato	I-2 (clone-2961)	DQ205968.1	243	26650.7	8.64	29.18	-0.239
Tomato	I-2 clone-2956	DQ205967.1	243	27315.5	7.64	32.31	-0.283
Tomato	I-2 (clone-2953)	DQ205966.1	242	27353.2	4.97	32.28	-0.331
Tomato	I-2 (clone-2944)	DQ205965.1	230	26076.8	5.03	32.47	-0.330
Tomato	I-2 (clone-3336)	DQ205964.1	243	27285.4	7.64	29.05	-0.281
Tomato	I-2 (clone-2962)	DQ205963.1	242	27413.2	4.97	30.47	-0.347
Tomato	I-2 (clone-2947)	DQ205962.1	236	26328.3	8.32	26.29	-0.240
Tomato	I-2 (clone-2954)	DQ205961.1	242	27353.2	4.97	32.28	-0.331
Tomato	I-2 (clone-3326)	DQ205959.1	243	27297.4	7.64	32.62	-0.272
Tomato	I-2-(clone-2943)	DQ205958.1	242	27111.4	8.32	30.01	-0.258
Tomato	I-2 (clone-3337)	DQ205957.1	243	27315.5	7.64	32.31	-0.283
Tomato	I-2 (clone-2948)	DQ205956.1	242	27327.1	4.97	33.08	-0.350
Tomato	I-2 (clone-3332)	DQ205955.1	243	27301.4	7.64	30.89	-0.284
Tomato	I-2 (clone-2958)	DQ205954.1	239	26832.0	8.33	29.82	-0.295
Tomato	I-2-Motelle	KR108299.1	1266	144801.0	5.87	49.43	-0.250
Tomato	I-2 (Heamsona)	FJ843082.1	52	5710.4	4.17	88.31	0.146
Tomato	I-2 (Complete cds)	AF118127.1	1266	144827.1	5.87	49.50	-0.252
Tomato	I-3-SRLK-4	KP082942.1	831	91960.3	5.62	39.57	-0.145
Tomato	I-3-SRLK-6	KP082944.1	834	93655.9	8.22	40.16	-0.185
Tomato	I-3-SRLK-5	KP082943.1	841	94589.8	6.97	37.97	-0.177
<i>Fusarium oxysporum f. sp. lycopersici (Fol) race 3</i>							
Tomato	I-7 gene	KT185194.1	966	108155.0	5.72	33.18	-0.097
Tomato	I-7 (Partial)	KT185195.1	953	106545.2	5.49	33.85	-0.091

Abbreviation: **pI:** Isoelectric Point, **I.I.:** Instability Index, **PI:** Protein length; **GRAVY**- Grand Average of Hydrophaticity

Table 4. Functional annotation of various defense categories genes (Resistance genes, Defense related enzymes, Multidrug resistance defense transporters and Transcription factors) of healthy bud stages.

Defense categories	Defense genes	Transcripts	Functions
Resistance genes	HBS-RAR1-1	CDS-3391-Unigene-3798	Ion binding isoform 1
	HBS-RPM1-1	CDS-9827-Unigene-10439	Disease resistance protein RPM1-like isoform x1
	HBS-RPM1-2	CDS-27292-Unigene-30952	Disease resistance protein RPM1-like isoform x1
	HBS-RIN4-1	CDS-16966-Unigene-17781	RPM1-interacting protein 4
	HBS-RIN4-2	CDS-16967-Unigene-17782	RPM1-interacting protein 4
Defense Related Enzymes	HBS-MAPK 1-3	CDS-4327-Unigene-4775	Mitogen-activated protein kinase 1
	HBS-CCR	CDS-26597-Unigene-29738	Cinnamoyl COA reductase 1 isoform 1
	HBS-SOD1-1	CDS-2107-Unigene-2419	Superoxide dismutase
	HBS-SOD1-2	CDS-6076-Unigene-6630	Chloroplast iron superoxide dismutase 7a
	HBS-NO	CDS-14924-Unigene-15645	No-associated protein chloroplastic mitochondrial-like
	HBS- GST	CDS-13322-Unigene-13987	Glutathione transferase GST 23-like
Multidrug Resistance Defense Transporters	HBS-ABC1-1	CDS-12136-Unigene-12771	ABC transporter a family member 1-like isoform x1
	HBS-ABC1-2	CDS-12137-Unigene-12772	ABC transporter a family member 1-like isoform x2
	HBS-MDR/TP	CDS-23367-Unigene-25014	Transporter associated with antigen processing protein 1
Transcription factors	HBS-TGA-1	CDS-12719-Unigene-13364	Transcription factor TGA4
	HBS-TGA-2	CDS-12722-Unigene-13365	Transcription factor TGA4
	HBS-E2F3	CDS-22592-Unigene-24031	Transcription factor E2FC-like
	HBS-ERF1	CDS-25273-Unigene-27631	Ethylene-responsive transcription factor 1b
	HBS-LHY-1	CDS-3899-Unigene-4341	Protein LHY-like isoform x1
	HBS-LHY-2	CDS-3900-Unigene-4342	Protein LHY-like isoform x1
	HBS-LHY-3	CDS-3901-Unigene-4343	Protein LHY-like isoform x1
	HBS-WRKY2-1	CDS-20027-Unigene-21049	Probable WRKY transcription factor 2-like
	HBS-WRKY2-2	CDS-28911-Unigene-34492	WRKY DNA-binding protein isoform 1
	HBS-WRKY22-1	CDS-12231-Unigene-12866	WRKY transcription factor 47
	HBS-WRKY33-1	CDS-10776-Unigene-11361	WRKY DNA-binding protein 33 isoform 1
	HBS-WRKY33-2	CDS-10777-Unigene-11362	WRKY DNA-binding protein 33 isoform 1
	HBS-WRKY33-3	CDS-22322-Unigene-23719	WRKY transcription factor 17
	HBS-WRKY33-4	CDS-22323-Unigene-23720	WRKY transcription factor 17
	HBS-WRKY33-5	CDS-22324-Unigene-23721	WRKY transcription factor 17
	HBS- HSP-1	CDS-14-Unigene-24	Kda class i heat shock
	HBS- HSP-2	CDS-45-Unigene-67	Kda class i heat shock protein
	HBS- HSP-3	CDS-128-Unigene-170	HSP20-like chaperones superfamily protein

HBS- HSP-4	CDS-147-Unigene-191	Small heat shock protein
HBS- HSP-5	CDS-384-Unigene-477	Kda class i heat shock
HBS- HSP-6	CDS-386-Unigene-478	Kda class i heat shock
HBS- HSP-7	CDS-388-Unigene-479	Kda class i heat shock
HBS- HSP-8	CDS-711-Unigene-850	Heat shock
HBS- HSP-9	CDS-972-Unigene-1175	Kda class iv heat shock
HBS- HSP-10	CDS-1080-Unigene-1296	Kda class iv heat shock
HBS- HSP-11	CDS-6558-Unigene-7113	Kda class iii heat shock protein
HBS- HSP-12	CDS-7318-Unigene-7893	HSP20-like chaperones superfamily protein
HBS- HSP-13	CDS-7342-Unigene-7917	Kda heat shock mitochondrial-like
HBS- HSP-14	CDS-11001-Unigene-11587	Kda class i heat shock
HBS- HSP-15	CDS-13462-Unigene-14140	Small heat shock protein
HBS- HSP-16	CDS-13463-Unigene-14141	Small heat shock protein
HBS- HSP-17	CDS-14070-Unigene-14763	Small heat shock protein
HBS- HSP-18	CDS-6102-Unigene-6658	Heat shock 70 kda
HBS-SHMT-1	CDS-12763-Unigene-13420	Serine mitochondrial-like
HBS-SHMT-2	CDS-12764-Unigene-13421	Serine mitochondrial-like

Table 5 Functional annotation of various defense categories genes (Resistance genes, Defense related enzymes, Multidrug resistance defense transporters and Transcription factors) of healthy bud stages and healthy panicle stages.

Defense categories	Defense genes	Transcripts	Functions
Resistance genes	HPS_RIN4	CDS_15840_Unigene_16444	Disease resistance protein at4g27190-like
	HPS_RPM1_1	CDS_23120_Unigene_24603	Disease resistance protein RPM1-like isoform x1
	HPS_RPM1_2	CDS_23769_Unigene_25459	Disease resistance protein RPM1-like isoform x1
	HPS_RPM1_3	CDS_26228_Unigene_29069	Disease resistance protein RPM1-like isoform x1
Defense Related Enzymes	HPS_CCR	CDS_8833_Unigene_9235	Mitogen-activated protein kinase 1
	HPS_GST_1	CDS_524_Unigene_628	Probable glutathione s-transferase-like
	HPS_GST_2	CDS_3267_Unigene_3623	Glutathione s-transferase TAU 7
	HPS_GST_3	CDS_3268_Unigene_3624	Glutathione s-transferase TAU 7
	HPS_ADH_1	CDS_1361_Unigene_1580	Alcohol dehydrogenase-like
	HPS_ADH_2	CDS_1362_Unigene_1581	Alcohol dehydrogenase-like
Transcription factor	HPS_TGA_1	CDS_7452_Unigene_7876	Transcription factor TGA2 isoform x1
	HPS_TGA_2	CDS_7453_Unigene_7877	Transcription factor TGA6-like isoform x4
	HPS_TGA_3	CDS_7456_Unigene_7879	Transcription factor TGA2 isoform x2
	HPS_TGA_4	CDS_7457_Unigene_7880	Transcription factor TGA6-like isoform x4
	HPS_TGA_5	CDS_7460_Unigene_7882	Transcription factor TGA2 isoform x2
	HPS_HY5	CDS_9402_Unigene_9830	Transcription factor
	HPS_E2F3	CDS_25180_Unigene_27426	Transcription factor E2FC-like
	HPS_ERF1	CDS_28026_Unigene_32402	Ethylene-responsive transcription factor 1b
	HPS_WRKY22_2	CDS_14327_Unigene_14839	WRKY dna-binding protein 33 isoform 1

	HPS_HSP_1	CDS_45_Unigene_69	Kda class i heat shock
	HPS_HSP_2	CDS_397_Unigene_487	HSP20-like chaperones superfamily protein
	HPS_HSP_3	CDS_399_Unigene_490	Small heat shock protein
	HPS_HSP_4	CDS_1187_Unigene_1389	Kda class iv heat shock
	HPS_HSP_5	CDS_2155_Unigene_2454	Kda class iv heat shock
	HPS_HSP_6	CDS_2241_Unigene_2550	HSP20-like chaperones superfamily protein
	HPS_HSP_7	CDS_6702_Unigene_7108	Kda class i heat shock
	HPS_HSP_8	CDS_20215_Unigene_21164	Kda heat shock mitochondrial-like
	HPS_HSP_9	CDS_30526_Unigene_38977	HSP20-like chaperones superfamily protein

ABSTRACT
**Identification of genes associated with mango malformation through
Differential Expression Analysis**

Mango, the King of fruits belongs to the family Anacardiaceae and occupies a paramount place among the fruit crops grown in India owing to its delicious flavour and taste. Out of several diseases that attack mango crop, malformation caused by *Fusarium mangiferae* is a serious threat to mango cultivation in various countries, since it causes 50-90% yield losses. Differentially expressed genes (DEGs) in healthy and malformed buds of mango variety Amrapali were identified and assessed through transcriptome analysis. The annotation of total unigenes sequences with NR (non-redundant) database, GO (gene ontology) analysis and COG (Clusters of Orthologous Groups) analysis were 96.74%, 52.28%, and 29.44% respectively. During HB-1 vs MB-1, HB-2 vs MB-2 and HB-2 vs MB-3 stages, more numbers of ethylene and auxin transcripts were up-regulated and among the protein kinases, LRR receptor-like serine/threonine-protein kinase, putative receptor-like protein kinase, CBL-interacting protein kinase and serine/threonine-protein kinase related transcripts were up-regulated. Upregulation of LDL2, TPL and WRKY transcripts at bud stages (HB-1 vs MB-1) and UBP-12, MYB30, AGL-24 and early flowering genes (ELF, EFS, REF6) at panicle development stages (HB-2 vs MB-2 & MB-3) were identified. More numbers of transcription factors related to WRKY (12), followed by ERF (6), and MYB (5) were up-regulated at HB-1 vs MB-1, HB-2 vs MB-2 and HB-2 vs MB-3 stages. The KEGG pathway analysis indicated that more number of differentially expressed transcripts for phenylpropanoid biosynthesis, flavonoid biosynthesis, amino acid pathway, oxidative phosphorylation, plant hormone signal transduction, AMPK, MAPK, and VEGF signaling pathways were observed at HB-1 vs MB-1, HB-2 vs MB-2 and HB-2 vs MB-3 stages. Gene networking analysis of DEG's inferred that HSP, SHMT, SOD, WRKY 33, MAPK, CCR, and LHY5 were actively involved in defence mechanism of healthy tissue (HB-1 & HB-2). Out of 65 *Fusarium* resistance gene sequences studied, 33 protein sequences were stable. The most commonly occurring protein motifs were motif-3 and motif-1. More number of *Fusarium* elicitor responsive CRE's (Box-W1 and EIRE) and biotic stress responsive CRE's (TC-rich repeats, CGTCA-motif, AT-rich sequence and TGACG-motif) were also observed in *Fusarium* resistance genes. These findings will serve as foundation for future functional studies and in genetic improvement programmes to develop variety resistant to mango malformation.

सार

विभेदक अभिव्यक्ति विश्लेषण के आधार पर आम के गुच्छा रोग से सम्बंधित जीन की पहचान

आम फलो का राजा है। यह अनाकार्डियेसी परिवार के अंतर्गत आता है। खुशबूदार और स्वादिष्ट फल होने के कारण, भारत में उगाए जाने वाले फलो में इसका एक सबसे महत्वपूर्ण स्थान है। आम की फसलों पर लगने वाली कई बीमारियों में से, फुजैरियम मेंजीफेरी के कारण हुई कुरूपता विभिन्न देशों में आम की खेती के लिए एक गंभीर समस्या है, क्योंकि यह 50–90 प्रतिशत तक फसल के को नुकसान पहुँचाती है। आम की आम्रपाली किस्म के स्वस्थ और विकृत कली में विभेदित रूप से व्यक्त जीन (डी ई जी) की पहचान की गई और ट्रांसक्रिप्टोम विश्लेषण के माध्यम से इसका मूल्यांकन किया गया। एनआर (गैर-अनावश्यक) डाटाबेस, जीओ (जीन ऑटोलोजी) विश्लेषण और सीओजी (ऑर्थोलॉजिक समूह के क्लस्टर) विश्लेषण के साथ कुल यूनिजीन अनुक्रमों की टिप्पणी क्रमशः 96.74%, 52.28% और 29.4% थी। एचबी-1 विरुद्ध एमबी-1, एचबी-2 विरुद्ध एमबी-2 और एचबी-2 विरुद्ध एमबी-3 चरणों के दौरान, अधिक संख्या में एथिलीन और ऑक्सिन ट्रांसक्रिप्ट्स विनियमित (अपरेगुलेटेड) हो चुके हैं और प्रोटीन कार्बोनेज के बीच, एलआरआर रिसेप्टर जैसे सीरिन ६ थ्रेऑनिन-प्रोटीन कार्बोनेज, तथाकथित रिसेप्टर जैसे प्रोटीन कार्बोनेज, सी.बी.एल.-इंटरैक्टिंग प्रोटीन कार्बोनेज और सेरीन ६ थ्रेऑनिन-प्रोटीन कार्बोनेज संबंधित ट्रांसक्रिप्ट्स विनियमित (अपरेगुलेटेड) हुए हैं। एलडीएल 2, टीपीएल और डब्ल्यूआरकेवाई ट्रांसक्रिप्ट कली अवस्था (एचबी-1 विरुद्ध एमबी-1) में विनियमित (अपरेगुलेटेड) हुए और पुष्पगुच्छ विकास चरण में यूबीपी -12, एमएबी 30, एजीएल-24 और जल्दी फूलों के (ईएलएफ, ईएफएस, आरईएफ 6) विनियमित (अपरेगुलेटेड) हुए जीन की पहचान की गई। एचबी-1 विरुद्ध एमबी-1, एचबी-2 विरुद्ध एमबी-2 और एचबी-2 विरुद्ध एमबी-3 चरणों में अधिक संख्या में प्रतिलेखन कारक से सम्बंधित डब्ल्यूआरकेवाई (12), के बाद ईआरएफ (6) और एमएबी (5) विनियमित (अपरेगुलेटेड) हुए। केईजीजी विश्लेषण में संकेत मिलता है कि एचबी -1 विरुद्ध एमबी-1, एचबी-2 विरुद्ध एमबी-2 और एचबी-2 विरुद्ध एमबी-3 चरणों में फिनाइलप्रॉपनोइड बायोसिंथेसिस, फ्लेवोनोइड बायोसिंथेसिस, एमिनो एसिड पाथवे, ऑक्सीडेटिव फॉस्फोरेलेशन, प्लांट हार्मोन सिग्नल ट्रांसडक्शन, एएमपीके, एमएपीके, और वीजेएफ सिग्नलिंग पाथवे के लिए भिन्न रूप से व्यक्त किए गए टेप (ट्रांसक्रिप्ट्स) की अधिक संख्या देखी गई थी। डीईजी के अनुमान के जीन नेटवर्किंग विश्लेषण में एचएसपी, एसएचएमटी, एसओडी, डब्ल्यूआरकेवाई 33, एमएपीके, सीसीआर और एलएचवाय-5 स्वस्थ ऊतकों (एचबी -1 और एचबी -2) के रक्षा तंत्र में सक्रिय रूप से शामिल थे। फुजैरियम के 65 प्रतिरोध जीन अनुक्रम के अध्ययन में से, 33 प्रोटीन अनुक्रम स्थिर थे। सबसे अधिक होने वाली प्रोटीन प्रस्तुतियां मोटिफ-3 और मोटिफ-1 थी। फुजैरियम प्रतिरोधी जीन में अधिक संख्या में फुजैरियम एलिसिटर उत्तरदायी सीआरई (बॉक्स-डब्ल्यू 1 और ईईआर) और जैविक तनाव संबंधी सीआरई (टीसी-समृद्ध पुनरावृत्ति, सीजीटीसीए- मोटिफ, एटी-अमीर अनुक्रम और टीजीएसीजी- मोटिफ) भी देखें। उपरोक्त निष्कर्षों में भविष्य के कार्यात्मक अध्ययनों के लिए आधार और आनुवांशिक सुधार कार्यक्रमों में आम की कुरूपता के प्रति प्रतिरोधी किस्म के विकास के लिए बुनियाद रखी जाएगी।